

Supporting Integration of Motivational Interviewing in HIV Service Organizations

With deep gratitude, we dedicate this bundle to the memory of
Bryan R. Garner, whose vision, leadership, and unwavering
commitment shaped the foundation of this work.

Table of Contents

<i>Introduction to the Resource Bundle</i>	4
<i>Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention at a Glance</i>	6
<i>Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention Manual</i>	10
<i>Tour of Motivational Interviewing</i>	11
<i>Online Tools for Practicing Motivational Interviewing</i>	12
<i>Supporting Integration of Substance Use Interventions in HIV Service Organizations</i>	14
<i>Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy Manual</i>	19
<i>Glossary of Terms</i>	22
<i>Appendix</i>	24

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Introduction

This resource bundle was developed to help AIDS Education and Training Centers (AETCs), Addiction Technology Transfer Centers (ATTCs), and other training and technical assistance (TTA) providers assist HIV service organizations with implementing and sustaining motivational interviewing (MI). MI is a person-centered approach that helps individuals explore and strengthen their own motivation for behavior change.

MI has a strong evidence base for promoting behavior change, particularly in reducing substance use—a major barrier to HIV care engagement and retention. Given the high prevalence of substance use disorders among people with HIV, AETCs and ATTCs play a key role in helping HIV service organizations (HSOs) implement this evidence-based approach to improve outcomes across the HIV care continuum.

The tools provided here are designed to meet organizations where they are, offering foundational knowledge, skill-building resources, and strategic guidance for long-term integration of MI into practice. Specifically, the tools aim to help organizations implement the MI Brief Intervention (MIBI) and sustain it over time using the Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF) Strategy.

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How to Use this Resource Bundle

This resource bundle contains information on and access to five resources that might be useful to TTA providers who work with HSOs. You can use each resources on its own or in combination, depending on your team's needs and goals.

MIBI at a Glance. This factsheet provides an overview of the MIBI, which is tailored to address risky substance use that can interfere with engagement in HIV care. It may be distributed as a standalone resource to HSO leadership and staff with an interest in learning more about MIBI.

MIBI Manual. This section introduces a step-by-step guide to the MIBI, intended for TTA providers to use when training and supporting HSOs. It outlines how HSO staff can deliver the MIBI and includes scripts, prompts, and resources to support implementation. The full manual can be accessed in **Appendix A**.

Tour of MI. This section provides information on a brief, five-module foundational course in MI, designed for staff at HSOs who are new to MI. It is meant to build foundational knowledge and skills as a first step before engaging in direct client interventions.

Online Practice Tools. This section presents two digital tools—Lyssn and SIMmersion—intended for service providers to develop, refine, and assess their MI skills. These tools are especially useful for ongoing practice and quality improvement following initial training.

Supporting the Integration of Substance Use Interventions in HSOs. This factsheet summarizes key findings from a study to assess the fit of 10 strategies that AETCs may use to support HSOs with implementation of interventions like the MIBI. It may be used by AETCs to identify which strategies will work best for them in a given context.

ISF Manual. This section provides information on the ISF strategy, which TTA providers can use to coach staff at HSOs seeking to implement the MIBI. The full step-by-step guide to using the ISF strategy can be found in the **Appendix B**.

Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention at a Glance: Addressing Risky Substance Use among People with HIV

Substance use disorders can adversely affect all stages of care for people with HIV, including engaging in treatment and sustaining HIV viral suppression.¹ Therefore, addressing risky substance use among people with HIV is key to supporting the Ending the HIV Epidemic initiative in the United States.^{2,3} The Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) is a tool that effectively addresses problematic substance use among people with HIV and is feasible to implement.⁴ HIV service organizations (HSOs) and others that support people with HIV can integrate this intervention to better support those in need.

✦ MIBI Overview

The MIBI is a 15- to 30-minute brief intervention delivered privately either in person or remotely and delivered once or over multiple sessions, depending on the needs of the client. Using motivational interviewing (MI), a facilitator guides a client to explore their reasons for change within an atmosphere of acceptance and compassion and encourages them to progress along the stages of change by eliciting change talk (**Figure 1**).⁵

Figure 1. The MI Hill and Stages of Change

This includes leveraging four overlapping tasks that build upon one another over the course of the conversation: Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan (**Figure 2**). The MIBI further involves following up with referrals to substance use treatment and community supports as needed.⁵

Figure 2. The Four Tasks of MI for Substance Use (Adapted from MIBI Manual)

◆ Does the MIBI Work?

MI is considered effective for addressing problematic use of alcohol, marijuana, and other drugs (e.g., cocaine, heroin) and increasing engagement in treatment for substance use disorder.⁶⁻⁸ When assessing the fit of nine evidence-based treatments for substance use disorder for HSOs in the United States to implement, MI was identified as having the greatest promise.²

The MIBI has been tested in HSOs and has been established as an effective tool for reducing risky substance use among people with HIV.^{4,9,10} The brief nature of the MIBI makes it feasible for HSOs to integrate into client care.

◆ Components

- Screening to identify risky substance use
 - 15- to 30-minute MI-based conversation tailored to the client
 - Referral to appropriate services as needed and follow-up on change plan if developed
-

◆ Staffing

The MIBI can be implemented by a range of service providers, including counselors, case managers, social workers, addiction specialists, nurses, and physicians, as long as they receive adequate training to provide it appropriately. Existing staff at HSOs can be trained to integrate the MIBI into care for clients.

◆ Resources

There are multiple resources available for providers and their supervisors to learn about MI broadly and the MIBI specifically.¹¹ Listed here are a sampling that may be especially helpful to those seeking to implement the MIBI for people with HIV and risky substance use.

Tour of MI. A free 4-hour, virtual self-paced training on MI that can provide continuing education certificates.

MIBI manual. A free 53-page manual that includes background on MI, an overview of the MIBI, and MIBI-specific scripts, materials, and handouts. Handouts include tools for MIBI conversations, such as a checklist to identify reasons for quitting or cutting back and a change plan contract. (See **Appendix A** for the full manual.)

Online practice tools. Tools leveraging artificial intelligence can provide interactive training and feedback. [Lyssn](#) provides feedback on real or practice MIBI session recordings to help providers improve facilitation skills, offering scores for empathy, active listening, affirmations, and more. [SIMmersion](#) offers virtual clients with who providers can role-play to practice delivering the MIBI.

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Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention Manual

The Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) manual is a guide for delivering a single-session MI meeting. MI is a collaborative conversation that strengthens a person's motivation and commitment to change by eliciting and exploring their reasons for change within an atmosphere of acceptance and compassion.

This manual offers step-by-step guidance for conducting an effective 15- to 30-minute MIBI session, including scripted language, personalized feedback strategies, and trauma-informed considerations. Whether a provider is new to MI or looking to reinforce their practice, the manual will help them integrate core MI principles—such as change talk, importance and confidence rulers, and collaborative goal setting—into your work clients.

This 53-page manual contains three sections:

- 1 Overview of MI.** This section provides a background and summary of MI, including its core spirit, evidence base, and foundational principles for effective behavior change conversations.
- 2 MIBI.** This section presents the brief intervention in a structured, step-by-step format. It includes both a full description of the intervention and a shorter version to guide case managers in the intervention steps. Sample scripts, suggested prompts to evoke change talk, and guidance on using tools like importance and confidence rulers to strengthen motivation are also included.
- 3 Materials, Resources, & Job Aids.** This section contains HIV-related materials and supplemental information regarding risks associated with different substances that can be used as resources when delivering the MIBI. Examples include personalized feedback tools (e.g., cost of use calculator, HIV care continuum), change plan templates, and client handouts on substance use and anti-retroviral therapy adherence.

◆ Access

To access the full manual, see **Appendix A:** Martino S, Speck K, Satre D, Vandersloot D, & Garner B. *MIBI Manual: Motivational Interviewing-Based Brief Intervention (MIBI) protocol for HIV-positive clients with risky substance use.* National Institute on Drug Abuse; 2023.

Tour of MI

A Tour of Motivational Interviewing: An Interprofessional Road Map for Behavior Change is a free 4-hour introductory course designed to provide a foundational understanding of motivational interviewing (MI). This course was prepared by the University of Missouri–Kansas City School of Nursing and Health Studies' Mid-America Addiction Technology Transfer Center under a cooperative agreement from the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration's Center for Substance Abuse Treatment and the National Institute on Drug Abuse.

MI is a collaborative conversation that strengthens a person's motivation and commitment to change by eliciting and exploring their reasons for change within an atmosphere of acceptance and compassion. Learners are guided through essential MI skills to strengthen an individual's motivation for behavior change. The course includes descriptions, demonstrations, and interactive activities designed to build initial competency. Four continuing education credits are available for completion.

Please note: This course does not offer full preparation for delivering MI with fidelity. Developing proficiency in MI is a gradual process that involves ongoing practice, skilled feedback from experienced practitioners, and opportunities for reflection and integration. Please reference other tools in the MIBI bundle for additional tools and resources to improve MI efficiency.

◆ Learning Objectives

Upon completion of the course, participants will be able to:

- Define the spirit of MI and examine its evidence base.
- Describe the importance of engaging the patient through core interviewing skills.
- Examine the ongoing process of seeking and maintaining a clear focus and strategic direction.
- Differentiate specific aspects of patient language that evoke and strengthen motivation and commitment for behavior change.
- Identify the components of planning for behavior change.
- Appraise interest in obtaining more advanced MI training and skill formation.

◆ Access

To register, navigate to www.healthknowledge.org and register for a free account. After registering, search for "Tour of MI" and click "REGISTER NOW AND BEGIN COURSE."

Online Tools for Practicing Motivational Interviewing

Two online tools, Lyssn and SIMmersion, leverage artificial intelligence (AI) to provide ongoing training and feedback to providers that implement motivational interviewing (MI) with their clients. [SIMmersion](#) offers virtual clients with whom providers can role-play to practice delivering MI. [Lyssn](#) provides feedback on MI session recordings to help providers improve facilitation skills.

◆ SIMmersion

SIMmersion provides AI-generated role-players that act as clients seeking support for a range of conditions, including alcohol and drug use disorders. SIMmersion uses its PeopleSim® technology to simulate conversations between a provider and a client. During the role-play, each statement made by the provider has 7–15 possible responses based on a probability calculation. Everything a provider says is rated based on the impact it has on the client and how the provider-client relationship evolves as a result.

MI Practice Details

The Brief MI role-player, “Gabe Turner,” has scored high on an alcohol use disorder screening test and has been asked to talk with a professional about his drinking habits. The provider meets with Gabe to motivate change in his drinking behavior. Gabe’s responses and choices depend on what providers say, his varying personalities, and a random selection.

The training includes a guide with information on MI techniques, a simulated conversation with Gabe to prepare providers for questions and pushback from clients, and comprehensive feedback during and after each play. SIMmersion recommends providers play three to five times, with each session taking approximately 20–30 minutes to complete.

Teaching objectives include:

- Creating a motivating conversation
- Using the MI process
- Using MI tools effectively

Access

Annual licenses for the Brief MI role-player are currently \$40. To learn more about using SIMmersion, visit its [webpage on MI](#).

◆ Lyssn

Lyssn is an AI-based training and quality improvement platform that assesses providers' fidelity to evidence-based practices, like MI. Providers submit recordings of conversations with clients and the platform suggests improvements to help the provider improve their technique. Lyssn is easy to use and HIPAA-compliant.

MI Practice Details

Lyssn aims to replicate feedback that would be provided by an expert clinical evaluator. The platform was built using academic research and over 26,000 human-rated psychotherapy conversations. Its evaluation metrics are based on research and standard evaluation tools used in academia and clinical practice for each evidence-based practice. Lyssn's MI metrics are based on spirit, empathy, reflection-to-question ratio, percentage of open questions, and percentage of complex reflections.

Organizations can use Lyssn for:

- **Training.** Providers can use training tools within Lyssn to engage in simulated clinical interactions.
- **Quality improvement.** Providers can upload recordings of real MIBI sessions with clients or directly record them within the platform and receive immediate feedback.
- **Documentation.** After uploading text, audio, or video of MIBI sessions, providers can receive a clinical summary using an organizational note template. Notes can be edited and finalized within the platform. Additionally, Lyssn offers searchable session transcripts.

Recordings are encrypted, protected by two-factor authentication, and can only be accessed by authorized users. After recordings are reviewed and providers receive feedback, the files can be deleted.

Access

To learn more about Lyssn, visit [Lyssn.io](https://lyssn.io). To begin using Lyssn, fill out their [“Contact Us” form](#). A sales representative will reach out to share pricing information.

Supporting the Integration of Substance Use Interventions in HIV Service Organizations

Substance use disorders (SUDs) impact every stage of the HIV care continuum, including increased risk of new infections, delayed testing and diagnosis, and reduced adherence to medication and viral suppression.^{1,2} Addressing SUDs among People with HIV is critical to achieving the goals of the “Ending the HIV Epidemic” initiative which aims to reduce new HIV infections in the US by 90% by 2030.³ Integrating SUD interventions into HIV service organizations (HSOs) is key to reaching this goal. Psychosocial interventions, like motivational interviewing, have shown promise for integration into HSOs. Supporting HSOs to implement psychosocial interventions may help them improve outcomes for people with HIV along the HIV care continuum.

The Health Resources and Services Administration’s AIDS Education and Training Center (AETC) Program is a national network of HIV experts who provide training and technical assistance to healthcare providers serving PWH. With eight regional offices and local partners, AETCs could serve as intermediaries to support the integration of effective SUD interventions into HSOs.⁴ Here, we present strategies AETCs can use to enhance the adoption, implementation, and sustainability of evidence-based interventions (EBIs) within HSOs.

◆ Potential Strategies to Support Integration

We engaged HIV, SUD, and implementation practitioners and researchers to identify 10 implementation strategies that some AETCs already use or could use to support HSOs in implementing psychosocial interventions that address substance use (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Overview of Implementation Strategies

The strategies have different resource requirements for AETCs to be able to carry them out successfully (e.g., what skills AETC staff would need to deliver the strategy, and the level of financial resources and time an AETC would need to devote to delivering the strategy) (Table 1).

Table 1. Approaches to Integrating Implementation Strategies within HSOs

Strategy	Details
EXPLORE	Disseminate EBI Information Increase the HSO’s knowledge about the intervention by identifying intervention-specific resources and sending them to leadership and staff.
	Conduct Formal Assessment Support the HSO in identifying service gaps and interventions to fill unmet needs by assessing community need and HSO readiness to fulfill that need.
	Obtain Formal Commitment Help grow the HSO’s commitment to implementing the intervention by encouraging leadership to commit to implementing the intervention.
PREPARE	Develop Implementation Plan Increase the extent to which the HSO is prepared to implement the intervention by engaging leadership and staff to determine necessary steps to implement.
	Provide Access to Training Modules Bolster the HSO’s understanding and perceptions of the intervention by providing staff with access to online modules and monitoring their completion.
	Conduct Interactive Training Workshop Develop intervention knowledge and skills within the HSO by conducting a workshop with staff that includes experiential exercises.
	Assess Provider Proficiency in EBI Skills Establish intervention competency within the HSO by using fidelity checklists and providing staff with feedback to ensure the intervention is delivered as intended.
IMPLEMENT	Provide Ongoing Clinical Consultation Improve intervention knowledge and skills within the HSO by convening staff in small groups to discuss cases and practice skills.
	Provide Ongoing Implementation Support Support the HSO in resolving implementation challenges by convening meetings with the implementation team and facilitating discussion to identify and address challenges.
	Facilitate Ongoing Learning Collaborative Help establish regular reflection and evaluation of the intervention implementation by convening meetings with implementation teams from several HSO to shares experiences and lessons learned and promote widespread and sustained delivery.

◆ Determining Strategy Fit

We engaged 64 representatives of AETC regional offices and local partners to determine the (a) importance of, (b) feasibility of, (c) readiness to offer, (d) scalability of, (e) pressure to offer, and (f) current need for the 10 strategies.⁵

Most participants (98.4%) agreed that integrating SUD-related services into HSOs is important. However, most reported that these services were currently integrated only to a moderate (52.5%) or minor extent (39.3%) within HSOs in their area and few participants indicated that their AETC is expected (21.7%), supported (40.7%), and rewarded (8.3%) to help HSOs integrate SUD-related services to a great extent.

Figure 4 presents the unadjusted Setting-Strategy Fit Index scores for each strategy, reflecting which ones are more promising for AETCs to use to help HSOs integrate SUD interventions. The figure includes the average contribution of the six items that comprise the index.

Figure 4. Total Setting-Strategy Fit Index Scores and Dimension Contributions

Disseminating information about the evidence-based intervention had the highest ratings for each dimension, resulting in the highest overall score (9.24) and the only strategy that had an unadjusted score that was significantly different from all other strategies. Providing access to asynchronous training ranked second (6.97) and was significantly different from all other strategies except from conducting a formal assessment, which had the third-highest score (6.70).

◆ **Selecting and Using Strategies**

The highest rated strategies (disseminating EBI information and providing training access) are one-direction, asynchronous, and easily sustained but offer limited tailored support. The set of strategies with overall scores in the middle (e.g., formal assessments, synchronous trainings, clinical consultation) require more interaction and resources. The lowest rated strategies (i.e., obtaining a formal commitment, developing an implementation plan, providing ongoing implementation support, and facilitating a learning collaborative) require AETC staff to have strong facilitation skills.

Although no single strategy may be a perfect fit, it's important to balance feasibility with potential impact. Different approaches vary in effectiveness and may contribute in distinct ways to achieving meaningful change. The information presented here on Setting-Strategy Fit can help AETCs consider the best option for their setting.

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Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy Manual

The Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF) strategy offers an evidence-informed approach to help organizations adopt, implement, and maintain evidence-based interventions (EBIs). In particular, it has demonstrated effectiveness in helping HIV service organizations and their staff implement the Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) for people with HIV who have risky substance use.¹ The ISF strategy works by providing a model to improve an organization's implementation climate (i.e., whether an intervention is expected, supported, and rewarded) while fostering a strong relationship between an external Implementation Advisor (IA) and the organization's implementation team.

The ISF manual provides necessary tools and strategies that will help IAs, and the implementation teams they work with, effectively navigate challenges, monitor progress, and create an environment where EBIs can become standard practice. Please note that this manual aims to provide guidance for the ISF specifically and does not go into the broader subject of facilitation.

In this 30-page manual, IAs will first review the foundations of ISF and then how to use the ISF by implementation phase.

✦ Foundations of ISF

Core ISF Strategies and Tools. The first section provides an overview of strategies and tools designed to engage an organization's staff in EBI implementation.

The ISF Relational Framework for Process Implementation. This section explains the four foundational framework elements of the ISF model. Each element illustrates the importance of an IA's role when using key ISF strategies and tools to strengthen the relationship between IAs and the implementation teams with whom they work.

The Four Processes of Motivational Interviewing (MI). Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan. This section gives a detailed review of the core MI principles and its four processes, which are referenced throughout the ISF manual. These processes provide an action plan that IAs can use to guide an organization through EBI implementation effectively.

◆ ISF by Implementation Phase

Initial Engagement & Planning. In alignment with the four MI processes, this section introduces tools to evoke reflection on factors that might impact implementation—either positively or negatively. Some tools that IAs will learn to use include the Implementation and Climate Evaluation tool; the Decisional Balance exercise; and Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats or Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results analyses.

Preparation for Implementation. This section introduces IAs to implementation preparedness through existing resources and mitigating limitations. For example, the Past Implementation Effort exercise is a way to reflect and understand past experience to improve implementation and help teams recognize strengths and overcome barriers. Identifying and preparing champions can ensure prepared support people are “on the ground” to help the implementation effort. Flowcharting can be used to plan for integrating the intervention into existing processes.

Active Implementation & Sustainment Planning. This section focuses on implementing and maintaining strategies through organized data-driven decision-making and consistent team involvement. ISF tools such as the Workbook Tracking Tool and Performance Review and Planning exercise help teams document progress, review performance data, and set clear goals while reinforcing the four MI processes.

◆ Access

The full manual may be accessed in **Appendix B: Roosa M, Garner B. Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF) Strategy. 2020.**

◆ References

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Glossary of Terms

AIDS Education and Training Center (AETC)

A national network funded by the Health Resources and Services Administration to provide education, training, and technical assistance to healthcare professionals and organizations treating people with or at risk for HIV. Learn more about the AETC program [here](#).

Addiction Technology Transfer Center (ATTC)

A national network funded by the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration to build local capacity for evidence-based substance use disorder treatment through training and technical assistance. Learn more about the ATTC program [here](#).

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Technology used to simulate human intelligence processes, such as providing feedback as applied in training tools like Lyssn and SIMmersion.

Change Leader (CL)

Leads the implementation effort internally and coordinates with the Implementation Advisor.

Decisional Balance (DB)

An exercise or tool used to weigh the pros and cons of implementing or not implementing an evidence-based intervention.

Evidence-Based Intervention (EBI)

A practice or intervention that has demonstrated effectiveness in achieving desired outcomes through scientific or practice-based research.

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV)

A virus that attacks the body's immune system, specifically the CD4 cells (T cells) that help fight infection. If left untreated, HIV can spread through certain body fluids (i.e., blood, semen, vaginal fluids, rectal fluids, and breast milk) and lead to AIDS (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome).

HIV Service Organization (HSO)

An organization that provides specialized support and services related to the prevention and treatment of HIV/AIDS.

Implementation Advisor (IA)

An external coach or consultant who supports the implementation of evidence-based practices using the Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation strategy.

Implementation and Climate Evaluation (ICE)

A tool to assess whether an organization's climate expects, supports, and rewards the implementation of an evidence-based practice.

Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF)

A structured strategy that leverages an external coach to help organizations adopt and sustain evidence-based interventions like the Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention.

Lyssn

An artificial intelligence-powered training and quality improvement platform that evaluates recordings of provider-client sessions to assess fidelity to evidence-based practices such as motivational interviewing.

Motivational Interviewing (MI)

An evidence-based, person-centered approach that helps individuals explore and strengthen their own motivation for behavior change.

Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI)

A structured, short-term application of motivational interviewing designed for brief encounters in settings such as HIV service organizations. It is typically delivered by case managers or service providers in one or two sessions and is adapted to fit the time constraints and needs of real-world service delivery.

Nominal Group Technique (NGT)

A structured brainstorming method used to ensure inclusion and prioritization of diverse ideas from implementation team members.

National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA)

Part of the National Institutes of Health, the National Institute on Drug Abuse supports scientific research on drug use and addiction, including its causes, consequences, prevention, and treatment, to inform evidence-based interventions like motivational interviewing.

Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA)

A rapid-cycle quality improvement model implementation teams use to test and refine changes to improve implementation of an evidence-based practice.

PeopleSim® Technology

SIMmersion uses PeopleSim technology to simulate conversations between a user and a virtual human role-player, or “client,” wherein each user statement has 7–15 possible responses and the PeopleSim technology selects a response based on a probability calculation.

Past Implementation Effort (PIE)

A reflective exercise that examines previous implementation experiences to inform an implementation team’s current planning and help them avoid past pitfalls.

Performance Review and Planning (PREP)

A data-driven tool that helps implementation teams evaluate recent performance and plan next steps to improve implementation.

Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA)

An agency within the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services that leads public health efforts to advance the behavioral health of the nation. SAMHSA provides funding, guidance, and resources to support mental health and substance use treatment and prevention.

SIMmersion

A virtual simulation platform that uses life-like role-play with digital “clients” to help providers practice communication and intervention skills, including motivational interviewing. Users receive real-time and post-session feedback to improve their motivational interviewing techniques.

Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results (SOAR)

A strength-based strategic planning tool that offers an alternative to Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats analysis.

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats (SWOT)

A strategic planning tool used to identify internal and external factors affecting implementation readiness.

Training and Technical Assistance (TTA)

An umbrella term that includes activities for helping organizations plan, implement, and evaluate innovative approaches. Examples of TTA providers include AIDS Education and Training Centers and Addiction Technology Transfer Centers.

Appendices

A *MIBI Manual: Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) Protocol for HIV-Positive Clients with Risky Substance Use*

B *Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy Manual*

MIBI MANUAL

Motivational Interviewing-Based
Brief Intervention (MIBI)
Protocol for HIV-Positive Clients
with Risky Substance Use

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CONTENTS

About the Manual	01
Introduction	02
Section I	
Overview of Motivational Interviewing	03
What is Motivational Interviewing?	03
Does MI Work?	05
How Does MI Work?	07
Can You Learn MI?	10
Section II	11
Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention	
Step 1	12
Step 2	14
Step 3	21
Step 4	23
Summary of Brief Intervention	25

CONTENTS

Section III	28
Materials, Resources, & Job Aids	28
Reasons for Quitting or Cutting Down Checklist	29
Feedback: Alcohol	30
Feedback: Cannabis	31
Feedback: Drugs	32
Feedback: Cost of Use	33
The HIV Care Continuum	34
ART & HIV	35
Drugs, Alcohol, & HIV	36
HIV and Injection Drug Use	38
Kicking the Habit: HIV and Smoking	38
Drugs and Alcohol: Points to Remember	38
Change Plan Contract	39
Section IV	
Appendices	40
Spirit of MI	41
Four Tasks of Motivational Interviewing	42
MI Hill: DARN CAT	43
Overview of MI	44
MI Flow Chart	45
MIBI Steps	46
Importance and Confidence Rulers	47
References	48

ABOUT THE MANUAL

What is MIBI?

Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) utilizes the foundational principles and values of Motivational Interviewing (MI) to deliver a similar intervention in a more concise and succinct way. The MIBI, designed to be conducted in a single session between 15-30 minutes, has been shown to be particularly effective with clients living with HIV who have, or are at risk for substance use disorder. Using the fundamental principles of MI, and building upon those, the MIBI is an easy to learn technique that may be easily incorporated into daily practice.

The Origins of MIBI

This manual will teach you how to deliver a Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) and was developed specifically to help reduce substance use in people living with HIV. Originally created and used in reproductive health care settings, the MIBI has been adapted for use by HIV Service Organizations. A 2014 research study confirmed the efficacy of this manual in the SAT2HIV research study that was funded by The National Institute on Drug Abuse (R01DA052294). The study results verified that the MIBI approach is successful in reducing substance use in people living with HIV. We hope you learn from it and implement it in your work.

INTRODUCTION

Hazardous substance use is both prevalent and problematic, yet it can be addressed through brief Motivational Interviewing (MI) based intervention. This manual is a guide to the delivery of a one-session MI meeting that we call a MIBI or Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention. This technique can be used in HIV/AIDS Service Delivery Settings with clients who have, or may be at risk for problematic substance use. Motivational Interviewing is an effective method to help motivate clients to cut down or stop using substances and to accept follow-up referrals to community substance use disorder treatment programs and self-help community supports.

The manual is divided into three sections. Section one presents an overview of MI, which is the foundation for our one-session brief intervention (MIBI). The second section covers the MIBI intervention, step-by-step. In this section, you will find both a full description of the intervention and a shorter version to guide case managers in the intervention steps. Section three contains HIV-related materials and supplemental information regarding risks associated with different substances that can be used as resources during the intervention. Appendices and references follow these sections.

SECTION I

OVERVIEW OF MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEWING

"a collaborative, goal-oriented style of communication"

WHAT IS MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEWING?

Miller and Rollnick¹ (p. 29), the originators of Motivational Interviewing (MI), define it as "a collaborative, goal-oriented style of communication with particular attention to the language of change. MI is designed to strengthen personal motivation for and commitment to a specific goal by eliciting and exploring the person's own reasons for change within an atmosphere of acceptance and compassion." This technique, grounded in the person-centered therapy approach initially developed by Carl Rogers, employs an empathic, supportive style of interacting with clients, which upholds their welfare, best interests, and potential for change. While person-centered, MI is distinct from non-directive approaches in that it has an intentional focus on moving people toward targeted change goals such as reducing alcohol or other substance use. MI presumes that most individuals feel some ambivalence about change, especially early in a session, and employs different strategies to assist in drawing out motivations for change.

During the Motivational Interviewing-based Brief Intervention (MIBI conversation), workers help identify change-oriented motives, encourage individuals to elaborate upon them, and work toward resolving ambivalence about change. Using the MI approach, clients are more likely to commit to a specific change goal and initiate behaviors toward a change plan. Four elements make up the core of MI: 1) partnering with clients, 2) non-judgmentally accepting their stance, 3) showing compassion, and 4) evoking the

clients' own arguments for change. These elements collectively represent the Spirit of MI.

A variety of MI strategies are used to build motivation during an interview. MI strategies aim to reduce arguments against change (sustain talk) and increase arguments for change (change talk). Workers take the time needed to determine what might make changing matter more, or feel more possible to the client, matching the interventions to the individual's level of motivation.

For example, moving too quickly toward planning for change with those who have not sufficiently resolved their ambivalence can result in the client feeling pushed into change, causing them to pull away from the process. When insufficient attention is paid to addressing important issues that interfere with change (for example, social pressure to continue substance use), people are more likely to raise these issues again. This is a signal for the worker to pause and reassess the individuals' thinking regarding the advantages and disadvantages of changing their behavior, the confidence level for change, and potential barriers to making a change. Alternatively, when a person is ready to move forward, to continue to extensively explore their motives for change may frustrate them, because they are now ready to make specific change plans or to put a plan into action.

When using MI, workers need to be clear about which behaviors are the targets for exploration and motivational enhancement. Motivation for change in one area does not guarantee motivation for change in another (e.g., a client may commit to cocaine abstinence, but not agree to reduce or stop drinking alcohol or smoking cannabis; or they might wish to try abstinence from substances on their own but not to enter an addiction treatment program). Each behavior may require a separate motivational conversation. MI also asks that a supportive and non-confrontational stance is taken about the preferred direction for change. For substance use, this direction is relatively clear in that most people would agree that it is ethically sound to help clients enhance motivation for reduction or cessation of potentially harmful substance use.

Other behavioral issues might not have a clear change direction that would be appropriate to promote. For example, decisions about organ donation or pregnancy termination likely would require a non-directive approach in which workers suspend their own values or goals and assume a neutral position. In these situations, a neutral and supportive client-centered approach allows clients to explore their ambivalence about sensitive personal issues without intentional influence. Once clients indicate their preference, moving in that direction to enhance motivation makes good sense.

DOES MI WORK?

Several recent reviews of the large body of MI research have come to some conclusions about how well MI works across a wide range of problem areas (e.g., alcohol, tobacco, drugs, gambling, diet/exercise, treatment adherence/engagement).⁴⁻⁶ In a review of MI, Brad Lundahl and his colleagues⁵ included 119 studies that isolated the unique effect of MI on treatment outcomes. The review concluded that across problem areas, MI exerted small, yet clinically significant effects, consistent with effects produced by other behavior change interventions and, in less time, while significantly increasing treatment engagement. The effects were durable, lasting up to one year. The largest area of MI research has been in its application to substance use problems, with evidence suggesting that compared to other well-established addiction treatments, MI is as effective for treating problematic drinking, cannabis use disorder, and problems with other drugs (e.g., cocaine and heroin, methamphetamine etc.).

Although alcohol and other drugs often present the most glaring problems in clients' lives, it is also important for workers to help clients assess their use of nicotine and,

like other potentially harmful substances, consider reduction or completely stopping. Nicotine products include cigarettes, cigars, pipe tobacco, and other smokeless varieties (e.g., chewing tobacco, snuff, dip, snus) and vapor products. Like heroin or cocaine, nicotine alters the way the brain functions, leading to the development of a substance use disorder. Use of nicotine is associated with poorer adherence to HIV antiretroviral

medications and reduces their efficacy. Regardless of the length of time a person has used nicotine, quitting brings immense benefits to overall health and wellness according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).⁷ MI can help patients make this important change. For example, Lindson, et al.,⁸ found MI may increase the possibility of long-term smoking cessation when used in combination with additional smoking cessation interventions such as nicotine replacement. While further evidence is needed, compared with non-MI smoking cessation interventions, there is a possibility that MI may enhance quit rates compared to other smoking cessation interventions alone (behavioral smoking reduction, contingency payments, health education counseling, brief advice, self-help materials).

Workers, including case managers, frequently serve persons who have experienced trauma. A history of trauma and other adverse life events may be important to consider in providing care to individuals with substance use problems. A large national survey⁹ found that 62% of the population had experienced at least one adverse experience (e.g., abuse, neglect, and/or household disfunction) before entering adulthood and many indicated they had experienced multiple negative life experiences. Exposure to adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) also is common among people with HIV.¹⁰ These experiences often result in detrimental effects on subsequent behavior, social and emotional development, and are associated with later experiences of trauma, anxiety, nicotine initiation, and other substance use problems.

Although this intervention model is brief (15-30 minutes) and is not designed to offer treatment for trauma or problems associated with it, a client's history of traumatic experiences calls for being trauma informed. Trauma-informed care¹¹ provides a model that recognizes how traumatic experiences impact mental health, substance use, and other disorders. Providing services for people with past traumatic experiences requires establishing a safe and trusting rapport with clients, which MI helps to nurture through being consistent with MI spirit, respect for client autonomy and collaboration, and demonstrations of empathy. In the context of brief interventions, workers can provide supportive, compassionate responses when clients share their trauma histories or describe other adverse events without eliciting specific details. If needed (e.g., if there is significant anxiety, depression, or impairment associated with past experiences), clients can be referred to mental health providers who are trained in evidence-based trauma-specific therapy.

Expressing empathy is crucial in MI. When clients feel understood, there is a greater likelihood they will be able to share their experiences about substance use, HIV, and commonly associated experiences like trauma. In one study, Moyers & Miller¹² found that receiving an intervention low in empathy had negative effects on treatment outcomes that were worse than no intervention at all, refuting the notion that any

treatment is better than none at all. Providing MI intervention skills to address substance use and common trauma-based service barriers such as missed appointments, avoiding change strategies, blaming others, and treatment refusal presents an opportunity to contribute substantially to positive outcomes.

HOW DOES MI WORK?

MI works through the clinicians' use of four overlapping tasks, which can be represented as stairsteps, each building upon one another over the course of the change conversation.¹ In this model, "each later process builds upon those that were laid down before and continue to run beneath it as a foundation." (p. 26). The tasks include engaging (connecting with clients and establishing a good working relationship), focusing (agreeing on the target of motivational enhancement and directing the conversation toward it), evoking (drawing out the clients' own motivations for changing the target behavior), and planning (developing commitment to change and formulating a specific plan of action). Moving flexibly between these processes in response to clients and acting as a guide rather than an expert during the MI conversations is the goal to be achieved.

Two main sets of MI practices are simultaneously in motion across the four overlapping tasks. First, core interviewing skills are used to build rapport, convey empathy, and clarify

the goals toward which the clients and workers move together. These skills include asking **open** (versus closed ended) questions more frequently to invite conversation about a topic, **affirming** positive aspects of the client, **reflecting** what the client has communicated, and **summarizing** periodically, referred to as the **OARS** of MI. In addition, mapping out an agenda, often through the exchange of information between clients and practitioners, is another core skill used to set a target to enhance motivation and provide an intentional direction in the interview.

Second, clinicians use specific practices to draw out clients' change talk and strengthen commitment for changing behaviors. Change talk statements include statements that prepare or build motivation for change, such as desire, ability, reasons, or need to make changes in behaviors (DARN), sometimes referred to as preparatory language about change, in that these statements represent the building of motivation that prepares someone to make a commitment to change. *Desire* statements indicate a clear wish for change (e.g. "I don't want my liver disease to get worse" or "I want to get my life back"). *Ability* statements indicate clients' beliefs that they can change, given their skills and available resources (e.g. "I was able to survive war, so maybe I can get my drug use under control"). *Reason* statements note the benefits of change and the

costs of not changing (e. g. “I will have better relationships if I stop using” or “If I don’t stop drinking, I doubt I can keep my job”). *Need* statements underscore how the problem behavior interferes with important areas of an individual’s life and how changing the behavior would likely improve matters (e. g. “I don’t even recognize myself; I can’t go on like this anymore”).

Change talk also includes statements that suggest people are mobilizing themselves for change. These statements involve commitment, activation, and taking steps to change (CAT). *Commitment* statements convey the stated intention to change (e. g. “My quit date will be this Thursday”). *Activation* statements indicate how people are getting ready to change (e. g. “I am going to call the program and see if I can get in”). Statements about *Taking Steps* to change are the strongest demonstration of commitment in that clients have put their words into action and are reporting these early efforts (e. g. “Instead of going to happy hour after work, I went to a recovery meeting”).

During the change conversation, client strengths are identified and expressed as motivation in each of these DARN / CAT areas of change talk and, to the extent needed, clients are encouraged to elaborate further (or talk about what has not been discussed)

to draw out more specific or additional motivations for change. For example, if a client clearly expresses desire, reasons, and need for change but had not discussed an ability to change, the client would be asked about their capacity or confidence in making a change. Lack of confidence is crucial to address, since the failure to believe in one's capacity to change may override one's belief that making a change is important. Strategically helping the client feel more able to change would make the most sense in this stage of the conversation. In short, statements regarding change continuously signal how to conduct an interview, like a navigation system guiding where to go. Multiple studies have found that use of MI-consistent interventions tailored to the clients' motivations increases the probability that ambivalence will resolve through the decrease of sustain talk and increase of change talk, which in turn, leads to good clinical outcomes such as reducing substance use.¹³ These findings underscore the importance of selectively eliciting and reinforcing change talk and softening sustain talk when conducting MI.

CAN YOU LEARN MI?

A variety of training resources exist to learn MI. These resources include textbooks, treatment manuals, training CDs, a supervision toolkit, online trainings, and an international training group, Motivational Interviewing Network of Trainers (MINT). Many of these resources are accessible at www.motivationalinterviewing.org.

Multiple modalities exist to learn MI. The most popular approach has been the use of multi-day workshops. Research on the effectiveness of MI workshops (expert-facilitated didactics and skill-building activities delivered in a group format) shows consistent improvement in attitudes, knowledge, and confidence in MI. Unfortunately, immediate skill gains resulting from the training diminish within a few months.¹⁴ Supervision that includes direct observation of sessions (via audio recordings), use assessment tools for performance feedback, and individualized coaching has been shown to be more effective in improving MI skills when it is used about monthly for 6 months following workshop training.¹⁵ Several MI assessment tools are available to reliably supervise MI practice in this manner.¹⁶ This approach to supervision is particularly important given that performance is more positively evaluated than when the same sessions are reviewed by their supervisors or independent judges.¹⁷ Moreover, in the absence of supervision in MI, workers may be more prone to initiate informal discussions (i.e., chat) about matters that are unrelated to their clients' treatment.¹⁸ Careful training and supervision in MI may help increase adherence to the skills. The NIDA-SAMHSA Blending Initiative product, called Motivational Interviewing Assessment: Supervisory Tools for Enhancing Proficiency (MIA: STEP),¹⁹ which is supported by the Addiction Technology Transfer Center (ATTC) Network, provides a number of helpful tools to learn MI and sustain skills over time.

MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEWING BRIEF INTERVENTION

Case managers will use MI to motivate clients with HIV to cut down or stop using substances and follow-up with referrals to community substance use disorder treatment programs and self-help community supports, as needed. The intervention takes 20-30 minutes to deliver and uses a step-by-step format to achieve its aims. The format is:

SECTION II

MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEWING BRIEF INTERVENTION

STEP 1: UNDERSTAND HOW THE CLIENT VIEWS THEIR SUBSTANCE USE AND HIV INFECTION

Step 1 aims to *engage* the client with the case manager and help them *focus* on primary substance use and having HIV. The components of MI spirit ought to mark the conversational style, and the case manager needs to be accepting, compassionate, and curious. Step 1 sets the tone of the intervention and increases the chance that the client will talk openly with the case manager. Recognizing

change talk, reflecting these statements, and encouraging elaboration on them is part of the process in Step 1. By the end of Step 1, the case manager may understand the client's level of motivation for stopping or cutting back on substance use and the client's understanding of how substance use may impact their HIV care.

Begin with a brief orientation to the intervention.

Thanks for providing me with information about your substance use. You informed me that [primary substance] is the substance that has caused you the most problems recently. If you are willing, I'd like to talk more about that, because people with HIV who smoke/drink/use [primary substance] or use other substances sometimes think about cutting down or quitting. This may or may not be true for you. No changes need to be made right now, I just want to get your thoughts about it and then we can talk about what you may want to do at this point. If you decide you want to quit or cut down, we can talk about options available to you that might help you make this change. You don't need to want to make any changes now or commit to anything, for us to have an initial conversation. How does that sound?

Thank the client for being willing to talk with you, and then ask the client about their use of [primary substance] use. You might ask the following open question or request:

How does your use of [primary substance] fit into your life?

As the client describes their use, reflect what is said to demonstrate you are listening and have an accurate understanding. For example:

Methamphetamine has caused a lot of problems for you over the past couple of years, to the extent that it has almost taken over your life. Being HIV positive hasn't helped you feel hopeful about improving your health and your living situation, and you have developed an attitude of, "What does it matter?" when it comes to using meth, since you have HIV anyway and have been pretty discouraged about that.

If the client's HIV status has not come up in the conversation, ask about it directly with another open question or request and then continue to reflect this information along the way:

How, if at all, do you see your HIV status and substance use as being connected?

Take note of the client's statements that indicate change talk and sustain talk and strategically reflect comments in a manner that lends support or emphasis to change talk.

For you, it's been hard not using meth. It's often all around you, living on the streets and being around people who also get high. On the other hand, meth keeps you on the streets and makes it much less likely that you will come here for help.

Use open questions, as needed, to encourage the client to elaborate more about issues that support not using meth or favor getting HIV care and treatment.

If you were to continue to use meth like you have been, how do you feel that will affect your health?

After discussing the client's substance use and HIV status, summarize what the client said.

You've said you have tried not to dwell on having HIV and this has been the main reason you have not stuck with treatment for it. In addition, you feel like other day-to-day issues, like having a safe place to live, finding a job, and family problems, are more pressing and get in the way of coming to treatment at this clinic. Making matters worse is your meth use. You have been using a long time, even before you knew you had HIV. While you have tried to do something to stop using meth in the past, it rarely has lasted for more than a few months and you keep returning to it. You might be willing to consider stopping again if you get the right kind of help.

Proceed to Step 2A.

STEP 2A: DISCUSS REASONS FOR CHANGING PRIMARY SUBSTANCE USE

Step 2 aims to build upon Step 1 by more strategically *evoking* change talk. Most likely, the client will have already provided some reasons that would support their ultimate substance use goal (cut down, maintain lower-level use, quit completely, stay quit, no change, unsure). Step 2 structures and expands the discussion within a decisional balance framework. The idea is to use this framework for enhancing motivation for change (i.e., if further exploration of the client's motivation for change would result in the client moving from the goal of not changing or being unsure to cutting down or quitting). This means that the decisional balance is conducted in a manner that, relatively speaking, gives more emphasis to and draws out change talk (reasons for quitting/cutting down/maintaining the change if already initiated) instead of sustain talk (reasons for using without change). Step 2 ends with a key question to determine the client's substance use goal.

Begin with a transition statement to Step 2A.

Let's talk more about what affects your decision about smoking/drinking/using [primary substance].

Start with reasons for using. Typically, the reasons for using consist of the benefits of using the substance (e.g., “It relaxes me.”) and the drawbacks of not using it (e.g. “I would have a hard time with cravings or urges to smoke.”).

- *If the client has not yet provided reasons for using, ask the following open question:*

What is your main reason for using?

- *If the client has already provided a reason for using, begin by first reflecting it and then use an open question to determine if there is anything else to add.*

So far, you've said that smoking is relaxing. What other reasons do you have for smoking cannabis?

Next, ask about the reasons for not using or for cutting down. These reasons are the benefits of quitting or cutting down (“I’ll have more money.”) and the costs of not changing the primary substance use (“I’m worried about my health.”). You can spend time exploring reasons for change as they surface to capitalize on change talk when you hear it. In addition, use the handout, *Reasons for Quitting or Cutting Down* to help prompt the client’s reasons. If the client has not yet provided reasons for quitting, cutting down, or has not already initiated a change in substance use, ask the following open question:

What might be [were] your reasons for quitting or cutting down? (*Next, followup with the handout.*) Here is a list of other reasons for quitting or cutting down. Please look at it and check off any other reasons that may apply to you.

- *If the client has already provided reasons for quitting or cutting back, begin by first reflecting the reasons and then ask the client to check off any additional reasons that may apply from the handout.*

Earlier you said that you are concerned about the negative effect smoking has had on your health. You really want to be healthy, and using nicotine produces is getting in the way of that. Here is a list of other reasons for quitting or cutting down. Please look at it and check off any other reasons that may apply to you.

Summarize what the client has said, linking together reasons to use and quit/cut down or maintain his/her change in use in a double-sided manner – ending on the side of reasons for change (to strategically give emphasis to it). Ask for the client’s reaction to this discussion and reflect change talk, as indicated.

You’ve been smoking cannabis for several years. Your main reasons for smoking are that it relaxes you and it often makes pleasurable things you do, like listening to music or hiking, that much better. You’ve also said you are worried about your health. You’ve continued to smoke despite having bronchitis, which has taken a long time to overcome, and you don’t feel it is good given your HIV. In addition, you’ve put on some weight. You feel like you eat too much unhealthy foods when you are high. Finally, with your children getting older, you would feel hypocritical if you said they couldn’t smoke, and you continued to do so. You want to be a better role model for them. In brief, you want to take better care of yourself so that you can take better care of your family. *[pause]*

If client needs more prompting to respond, ask:

What do you make of all of this?

Ask the client what his/her current primary substance use goal is (quit completely, stay quit, cut down, maintain lower-level use, no change, unsure) or simply reflect it if the client has already expressed an intention to change.

You’ve said you drink heavily on occasion, especially at night if you have had an argument with your partner. While you feel you have not developed a huge drinking problem, you believe you could be heading in that direction and that makes you uncomfortable. You worry that you might drink and drive or end up meeting someone else at a bar just to spite your partner. You don’t want to put anyone else at risk. You think it might make sense to cut down or quit drinking all together. What do you think you want to do about your drinking at this point?

For a client who indicates they intend to quit completely, stay quit, cut down, or maintain lower-level use already initiated, proceed to Step 3. For a client who indicates an intention to keep using at current levels or who remains unsure about what she intends to do, proceed to Step 2B.

STEP 2B: PROVIDE PERSONALIZED FEEDBACK

Step 2b aims to strategically *evoke* change talk using *personalized feedback*. Personalized feedback attempts to increase the client's concern about their substance use. It falls within a category of interventions that develop discrepancies between the client's drug use and preferred goals, values, circumstances, or self-perceptions. The key to this technique is to maintain a collaborative

and objective tone. It is up to the client to determine what they make of the feedback and how it affects their motivation for change. To the extent the feedback process elicits change talk, the case manager reflects it and encourages the client to elaborate. The worker selects feedback forms to address the unique issues of the clients. Feel free to use only one or two forms in the order that makes sense. For some clients you may choose only to use the "cost of substance use" form or the "ART and HIV" form both found in Section 3 of this manual. The available feedback forms in that section include:

- Number of Alcohol/Cannabis/Drug Users
- Cost of Substance Use
- ART and HIV Care Continuum
- Drugs, Alcohol, Nicotine and HIV

Begin with a transition statement to Step 2B.

I'd like to provide you with some feedback about your use of [primary substance], including the effects of substance use on people who are HIV-positive. Along the way, I will be interested in what you think about the information. Would that be okay with you?

Review with the client how their primary substance use compares to other people. (Number of Alcohol/Cannabis/Drug Users Form)

First, here is some information about how your use compares with other adults in the United States. Only 1-2 out of every 100 adults use any drugs each month and even fewer adults use any specific drug, like methamphetamine. In other words, most people don't use meth or any other drug. It just might not seem that way if you are used to being around others who use meth or other drugs. What do you make of that?

Review with the client how much they spend on average per day on meth. Calculate per year the total amount and inform the client of it. Ask the client what else they could have bought with that amount of money. (Cost of Substance Use Form)

Money spent is another interesting area to look at. How many days do you use meth in a typical week? And how much would you say you spend on meth each day you do it? Okay, looking at the chart, if you use meth X days per week and spend on average \$Y per day on it, then you are spending \$YY per year. What do you make of that? If you could go back in time a year, what else would you do with that money?

Review with the client the HIV Care Continuum handout. Areas of feedback include:

- **It is essential for people with HIV to be linked to medical care including antiretroviral therapy (ART), to be retained in care (having regular appointments with their provider) and to achieve viral suppression (undetectable viral load).**
- **Alcohol, nicotine use and other drug use can interfere with each of these important steps in the care continuum, e.g., through worse self-care, missed medical appointments, lack of monitoring your viral control, and running out of medication.**

Inquire about how substance use has affected their HIV and broader medical care.

Staying connected to your health care providers is important to have consistent access to ART and also to manage other medical conditions you may have. How have you noticed that drinking or other substance use has had an impact on your HIV care?

Review the ART and HIV handout with the client. Areas of feedback include:

- **People who consistently take ART as prescribed have a much better chance of survival (viral load goes down and CD4 count goes up).**
- **Drinking and drug use significantly decrease the likelihood that people will take ART consistently.**
- **By reducing or stopping problematic drinking or drug use, people can improve their ART adherence and improve their health.**

After presenting this information, give the client an opportunity to respond and reinforce change talk. Inquire about how drinking or drug use has affected their ART adherence and what they might want to do about that.

Prior to ART medications being available, most people who were HIV positive died within a few years. Since ART was introduced, most people who take them consistently are living for a long time. Now, someone who contracted HIV at age 20 is likely to live 30-40 more years when they take ART properly. What do you think about this? How has drinking or other substance use affected your ability to take your medications properly?

Briefly review some of the main points in the Drugs, Alcohol, and HIV handout.

Points for feedback include:

- **HIV weakens your immune system, leaving you more vulnerable to contracting infections and disease.**
- **Alcohol, drug, and nicotine use weaken your immune system and increase risk for other non-HIV infections and diseases, making managing HIV much harder.**
- **HIV medications produce waste products that are processed through your liver. Drinking or using drugs taxes the liver, which may cause HIV medications not to work as well as they should.**
- **Sometimes the combination of HIV medications with drugs can cause unexpected and dangerous effects. For example, ritonavir (Norvir) can hamper your body's ability to break down amphetamines in your system, boosting their levels in your bloodstream, thereby increasing the risk of overdose and severe drug reactions.**
- **Drinking and drug use increase the risk for unsafe sex, which could put your sexual partners at risk for HIV or you at risk for other STDs.**

Here is a handout that describes the relationship between drugs, alcohol and HIV. As we go over some of the main points, I'm interested in what you think about this information. [Go over some of the bulleted points above.]

Summarize the client's reactions and emphasize anything they say that favors changing substance use. End with a key question to determine the client's readiness for change.

You were quite surprised to learn that few people use meth and even more surprised about the amount of money you are spending to support your use. You've told me how many problems you have had with meth. For instance, you typically don't eat well and often feel hungry, especially when you've been experiencing homelessness. Being unhoused has been very unsafe and you have been the victim of physical and sexual assaults in the past. You might have even gotten infected with HIV from one of these instances. These

problems overwhelm you, so much so that you turn to meth to forget about them. You wonder what to do from here. What if anything, do you feel ready to do about your use of meth at this point?

For a client who indicates they intend to quit completely, stay quit, cut down, or maintain a lower-level use that they have already initiated, proceed to Step 3. For a client who continues to indicate an intention to keep using at current levels or who remains unsure about what they will do to proceed to Step 2C.

STEP 2C: ADDITIONAL MOTIVATIONAL ENHANCEMENT STRATEGIES

If after exploring reasons for change and receiving personalized feedback, the client continues to be uncertain about cutting back or quitting substance use, the case manager should use additional MI strategies to *evoke* motivation for change. Options include:

If the client **does not believe stopping substance use is important enough**, try the following:

- Ask: What would make quitting matter enough for you to change your substance use?
- Use the Importance Ruler strategy. (See Image Below)
- Ask the client to look into the future under the circumstances of no change in use and if they were to stop use.
- Ask the client what the worst thing is that could happen if they tried to stop using meth for a trial period and what the best thing is that could happen.

If the client **does not believe she is able to stop using**, try the following:

- Ask: What would need to happen for you to feel more able to quit?
- Use the confidence ruler technique. (See Image Below)
- Ask the client about past successes in cutting down or stopping substance use (or about successes in any other areas of their life) and how the client might apply these experiences to their present situation.
- Ask the client to identify their personal strengths or prior experience in making changes, have the client describe them to you, and ask the client how they might use these strengths to stop using meth.
- Ask the client to describe the main obstacles to change and brainstorm some possible options that might remove them.

Importance or Confidence Rulers

After one final attempt to enhance motivation for change, ask the client again about their goal. If the client commits to cutting down or quitting substance use, you will proceed to Step 3 and develop a change plan. If the client remains uncommitted, the case manager can ask the client's permission to share with him or her treatment options and resources that could be used in the future if the client decides to make a change later.

STEP 3: DEVELOPING A CHANGE PLAN

The case manager develops a *change plan* to strengthen the client's commitment to cut back or quit substance use. (You can use the form found in Section 3 to create and document the plan.) A very important aspect of developing a change plan is to identify "when" the client should use the change plan. For example, if the client's change plan to reduce drinking is to "have a non-alcohol drink between each

alcoholic drink”, it is important to help the client specify when this plan will be used. For example, rather than having the client say “I will have a non-alcoholic drink between each alcohol drink,” the goal would be to have the client say something like: “**When** I go out for drinks with my friends, I will have a non-alcoholic drink between each alcohol drink.” Thus, the main thrust of change planning should be to have the client identify when they intend to implement the change plan. The more specific and clear the “when” is stated, the more likely it is that the client will employ their change plan.

Keep in mind, however, that Change Planning is not about telling the client what they should do to change. Rather, it is to help the client identify what they are ready, willing, and able to do to reach their goal. For example, some clients may not be interested in substance use treatment referrals and instead may elect to change on their own. Consider discussing with these clients the ways they can help themselves:

- Set a “quit” or “cut down” date
- Tell others about your plan to change
- Get rid of things that remind you of using
- Practice outlasting urges and cravings by delaying use
- Develop other skills and strategies for dealing with low mood or anxiety
- Understand and manage aftermath & feelings related to trauma
- Avoid people, places and things that might trigger you
- Distract yourself with new, healthy, and pleasant things
- Use mobile apps tools to track drinking level, improve sleep, reduce worry
- Ask for help from friends
- Go online for support:
 - www.alcoholscreening.org
 - www.addictionrecoveryguide.org
 - <http://women.smokefree.gov/>
 - www.rethinkingdrinking.niaaa.nih.gov
 - quitnowapp.com/en

MI skills remain important during change planning, as some clients become ambivalent again as they think about committing to a plan. Reflecting their hesitations and coupling them with prior change talk may help resolve ambivalence, re-engaging them in the change planning discussion.

Ask the client what steps they are willing to take to quit or stop using substances. Remember to explore with the client where, when, and how each identified step will be employed.

How do you want to approach stopping your substance use? What steps or things will you do to help you reach this goal?

Describe the substance use treatment and self-help supportservices available in the area.

Ask the client about their interest in including any of these services as part of the change plan.

In addition, ask who else might help the client achieve their goals.

Who else can help you stop using meth? What specifically do you think they could do that you would find helpful?

Ask the client about obstacles that might come up and how the client might handle them if they were to occur.

What might interfere with your effort to change or be an obstacle for you? How would you handle that?

STEP 4: SUMMARIZE

The final step of the MIBI, Step 4, involves summarizing your conversation with the client whether or not they have decided to make any changes in their behavior. It is important to acknowledge the conversation and thank them for their participation, while continuing to use supporting language. Think about the Spirit of MI in this final step: Partnership, Acceptance, Compassion and Evocation are at the core of motivational interviewing.

If the client committed to change and developed a change plan, finalize the Change Plan Contract (found in section 3) to summarize the change plan and fortify commitment to it.

Thank you for talking openly with me about your use of meth and living with HIV. You've been smoking meth a long time and have decided that you are going to stop using it for several reasons, the main one being that you want to live with dignity and that means taking better care of your health. You hope that one day you can go back to school and become a counselor so that you can help other people who have similar problems to the ones you have experienced. One day, you also would like to have a stable and loving relationship with someone, and you realize continuing to use meth is only getting in the way of that.

To summarize your plan, let's go over your Change Plan Contract and then we both can sign it as an indication of our commitment to work together toward your goals. It says that you intend to [restate the goals] and you will try to achieve this by [restate the specific change option(s) selected]. If you agree, please sign the contract here. [The case manager also signs it.] Signing it is like making an agreement with yourself. I'll sign it also to show you my support for your decision and plans. How would you like me to check in with you? Text/phone, email?

For a client who remains unsure about changing substance use, thank them for considering the issue and encourage the client to discuss the issue again the next time they come in. Keep the door open. The client might also decide to quit or cut down in the future and is free to pursue any of the referral options, including changing on their own, at that point.

For a client who intends to keep using their primary substance unchanged, thank the client for talking about it with you. Summarize the client's perspective and be sure to include anything the client said that indicates some ambivalence about continuing to use. Inform the client that they can feel free to discuss substance or nicotine use again in the future with the staff at the agency. Keep the door open.

SUMMARY OF THE BRIEF MI INTERVENTION

Step 1: Engage & Focus

Understand Primary Substance Use

- Begin with a brief orientation to the intervention.
- Ask the client about their primary substance use and its connection to HIV.
- As the client describes their use, reflect what the client says to demonstrate you are listening and have understood.
- Take note of the client's statements that indicate change talk and sustain talk and strategically reflect comments in a manner that lends support or emphasis to change talk.
- Use open questions, as needed, to encourage the client to talk more about their point of view and elaborate on change talk.
- After discussing the client's primary substance use, summarize what they have said.

Step 2: Evoke

Step 2a: Discuss reasons for quitting/cutting down

- Begin with a transition statement to Step 2a.
- Start with reasons for using.
- Next, ask about the reasons for not using or cutting down. Use the handout "Reasons for Quitting or Cutting Down."
- Summarize what the client has said, linking together reasons to use and quit/cut down in a double-sided manner.
- Ask for the client's reaction to this discussion and reflect change talk, as indicated.
- Ask a key question to determine what the client intends to do at this point about their substance use.
- If a change goal is endorsed (quit completely, stay quit, cut down, or maintain lower-level use), proceed to Step 3. If the client does not intend to change or remains unsure, proceed to Step 2b.

Step 2b: Provide Personalized Feedback

- Begin with a transition statement to Step 2b.
- Review with the client how their quantity or frequency of use compares to other adults. Use the handouts for alcohol, cannabis, and other drugs.
- Using the chart, calculate the total amount the client spends per year on their primary substance. Ask the client what they make of it and what else the client thinks they could buy with that amount of money.
- Ask the client if they would like to know more about problems related to substance use for people with HIV.
- Summarize the client's reaction and give emphasis to anything they say that favor making a positive change in their use.
- End with a key question to determine readiness for change.
- If a change goal is endorsed (quit completely, stay quit, cut down, or maintain lower-level use), proceed to Step 3. If the client does not intend to change or remains unsure, proceed to Step 2c.

Step 2c: Enhance Motivation More

- If the client does not believe reducing or stopping their substance abuse is important enough, try the following:
 - Ask: "What would make quitting or cutting down matter enough for you to change your substance abuse?"
 - Use the Importance Ruler strategy
 - Ask them to look into the future under the circumstances of no change in use and if there were to stop or cut down their use
 - Ask the client what the worst thing is that could happen if they tried to stop or reduce use for a trial period and what the best thing is that could happen
- If the client does not believe they are able to cut down or stop using their primary substance even the client wants to try the following:
 - Ask: "What would need to happen for you to feel more able to quit or cut down?"
 - Use the Confidence Ruler strategy
 - Ask the client about past successes in cutting down or stopping substance abuse (or in any other areas of their life) and how they might apply these experiences to the present situation
 - Ask the client to identify personal strengths, have them describe them to you, and ask the client how they might use these strengths to cut down or stop using the primary substance
 - Ask the client to describe the main obstacles to change and brainstorm some possible options that might remove them
- In either case, offer the client information (of the brochure) about different change options and review them with the client for the future if the client decides to try counseling, seek medication assistance, or access other self-help or support services.

Step 3: Plan

Develop a Change Plan

- If the change goal needs clarification, ask the client about what their exact **goal** is (e.g., either quitting or cutting back).
- Ask the client what **steps** they will take to change. Identify **when** each step will be used.
- Review other **services** available in the area with the client (counseling, self-help/12-Step talk with health care professionals, medication, online resources, mobile apps, change on my own) and determine if the client has any interest in them. If so, again sufficiently detail when the client will make use of selected options.
- Ask the client who else might **support** their effort to achieve this goal to cut down or quit and how this might happen.
- Ask the client about **obstacles** they anticipate might come up and how the client might handle them if they were to occur.

Step 4: Summarize

Summarize & Support What the Client has Elected To Do

- For a client who has committed to change and has developed a change plan, thank them for considering the issue, summarize the main components of their motivation for change and how the client intends to change, and affirm the client for their participation in the interview and plans for change. Complete the Change Plan Contract as a final means to summarize the plan.
- For a client who remains unsure about changing substance use, thank them for considering the issue and encourage the client to discuss the issue again the next time they come in. Keep the door open. The client might also decide to quit or cut down substance use in the future and is free to pursue any of the referral options, including changing on their own, at that point.
- For a client who intends to keep using their primary substance unchanged, thank the client for talking about it with you. Summarize the client's perspective and be sure to include anything the client said that indicates some ambivalence about continuing to use unchanged. Inform the client that they can feel free to discuss their substance use again in the future with the staff at the agency. Keep the door open.

SECTION III

MATERIALS, RESOURCES, & JOB AIDS

The pages that follow may be used with your client to support you MIBI session. These materials may be printed and used as resources and fact sheets to provide supporting evidence to help your client.

Reasons for Quitting or Cutting Back

Please check all that apply to you

I WOULD HAVE MORE MONEY FOR THINGS.

I WOULD FEEL BETTER ABOUT MYSELF.

I WOULD BE HEALTHIER.

I MIGHT BE A BETTER PARENT.

I WOULD BE SAFER.

I WOULD LOOK BETTER.

I WILL BE LESS LIKELY TO HAVE RISKY SEX.

I WOULD BE LESS LIKELY TO GET IN TROUBLE WITH THE LAW OR LOSE MY DRIVER'S LICENSE.

I WILL BE MORE LIKELY TO GO TO MY HIV MEDICAL APPOINTMENTS.

MY FAMILY AND FRIENDS WILL STOP NAGGING ME.

I WOULD FEEL MORE RIGHT WITH MY RELIGIOUS BELIEFS OR GOD.

I WOULD GET ALONG BETTER WITH MY FAMILY.

MY CHILD OR CHILDREN WOULD NEVER SEE ME DRINKING TOO MUCH.

I WOULD BE LESS LIKELY TO LOSE MY CHILD OR CHILDREN.

MY FAMILY AND FRIENDS WOULD HAVE A MORE POSITIVE VIEW OF ME.

I WOULD BE MORE ABLE TO GET A JOB OR TO PERFORM BETTER AT MY WORK.

I WOULD FEEL THAT I WOULD BE MORE ABLE TO HELP RATHER THAN HURT MY COMMUNITY.

I WOULDN'T FEEL BAD OR SICK FROM DRINKING OR BECAUSE OF WITHDRAWAL.

I WILL BE MORE LIKELY TO TAKE MY HIV MEDICATIONS THE WAY THEY ARE PRESCRIBED.

NOTHING. I REALLY DON'T SEE ANY GOOD REASON TO QUIT OR CUT DOWN.

FEEDBACK--ALCOHOL

Adults reported the following statistics regarding their consumption of alcohol.

Binge Drinking in the Last Month
4 drinks for women; 5 drinks for men in a single occasion

Heavy Drinking in the Last Month
5 or more drinks on a single occasion on each or 5 or more days

FEEDBACK--CANNABIS

Adults reported the following statistics regarding their use of cannabis in the last month.

Cannabis Smoking in the Last Month

FEEDBACK--DRUGS

Adults reported the following statistics regarding their use of drugs in the last month.

**Drug Use in the Last
Month**
1-2 Adults

FEEDBACK--COST OF USE

Looking at the chart, if you use [primary substance] X days per week and spend on average \$Y per day on it, then you are spending \$YY per year.

Number of Days Primary Substance Used Per Week

Average Amount Spent Per Day (\$) on Primary Substance

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	52	104	156	208	260	312	364
2	104	208	312	416	520	624	728
3	156	312	468	624	780	936	1092
4	208	416	624	832	1040	1248	1456
5	260	520	780	1040	1300	1560	1820
6	312	624	936	1248	1560	1872	2184
7	364	728	1092	1456	1820	2184	2548
8	416	832	1248	1664	2080	2496	2912
9	468	936	1404	1872	2340	2808	3276
10	520	1040	1560	2080	2600	3120	3640
11	572	1144	1716	2288	2860	3432	4004
12	624	1248	1872	2496	3120	3744	4368
13	676	1352	2028	2704	3380	4056	4732
14	728	1456	2184	2912	3640	4368	5096
15	780	1560	2340	3120	3900	4680	5460
16	832	1664	2496	3328	4160	4992	5824
17	884	1768	2652	3536	4420	5304	6188
18	936	1872	2808	3744	5680	5616	6552
19	988	1976	2964	3952	4940	5928	6916
20	1040	2080	3120	4160	5200	6240	7280
25	1300	2600	3900	5200	6500	7800	9100
30	1560	3120	4680	6240	7800	9360	10920
35	1820	3640	5460	7280	9100	10920	12740
40	2080	4160	6240	8320	10400	12480	14560
45	2340	4680	7020	9360	11700	14040	16380
50	2600	5200	7800	10400	13000	15600	18200
75	3900	7800	11700	15600	19500	23400	27300
100	5200	10400	15600	20800	26000	31200	36400

THE HIV CARE CONTINUUM

The HIV care continuum is useful for both an individual-level tool to assess care outcomes, and a population-level framework to analyze the proportion of people with HIV in a given community who are engaged in each successive step.

Prevalence-based HIV Care Continuum, U.S. and 6 Dependent Areas, 2019

Note: Receipt of medical care was defined as ≥ 1 test (CD4 or VL) in 2019. Retained in medical care was defined as ≥ 2 tests (CD4 or VL) ≥ 3 months apart in 2019. Viral suppression was defined as < 200 copies/mL on the most recent test in 2019. Linkage to care is defined as having ≥ 1 CD4 or VL test within 30 days (1 month) of diagnosis. (Linkage is calculated differently from the other steps in the continuum, and cannot be directly compared to other steps.)

ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY

- The goal of ART (antiretroviral therapy) is to achieve an undetectable viral load. When a person with HIV achieves an undetectable viral load, they cannot transmit the virus sexually. A motivating message the US government has been encouraging through the NIH, CDC and HRSA is “Undetectable = Untransmittable”. This messaging reduces stigma and can help improve medication adherence and health outcomes.
- Cutting back or quitting alcohol or drugs increases the chance people living with HIV will take ART consistently as prescribed and achieve the desired undetectable viral load:
 - When people on ART drink alcohol, they are 9x more likely to not take their antiretroviral medication.
 - The more people drink, the more likely they will not take ART (Only 31% of heavy drinkers consistently take their medications).
 - Only 39% of people on ART who use drugs consistently take their medications.
- ART medications help increase immune cells essential for fighting infection (CD4 count) and reduce the amount of virus in the bloodstream (viral load) with the ultimate goal of reaching “undetectable” or below the limit of the blood test. Both delay the onset of symptoms and progression to AIDS, prolonging the lives of people living with HIV. For example, at age 20, life expectancy has now increased 30 to 40 years if people take ART medication properly. The latest HIV drugs now predict a near-normal life expectancy.

DRUGS, ALCOHOL AND HIV

Copied directly from <http://www.hiv.va.gov/patient/daily/alcohol-drugs/single-page.asp> (accessed October 21, 2020). This URL is no longer in use.

DRUGS AND ALCOHOL: OVERVIEW

If you've just found out that you are HIV positive, you might be wondering what alcohol and other "recreational" drugs will do to your body. (Recreational drugs are drugs that aren't used for medical purposes, such as beer, cocaine, and pot.) You may be wondering whether drugs are bad for your immune system. And what about your HIV medications--can recreational drugs affect those?

Nobody can say for sure whether using alcohol or other drugs is bad for you. Each person is different, and a lot depends on which drugs you use and how often you use them. However, most experts would agree that, in large amounts, drugs and alcohol are bad for your immune system and your overall health. Remember, if you have HIV, your immune system is already weakened. Here, you can read about what alcohol and drugs can do to your overall health.

DRUGS AND ALCOHOL: EFFECTS ON YOUR IMMUNE SYSTEM

Drinking too much alcohol can weaken your immune system. A weaker immune system will have a harder time fighting off common infections (such as a cold or COVID-19), as well as AIDS-related infections. A weaker immune system also increases the chance that you will experience more side effects from your HIV medications. Smoking cannabis (pot) or any other drug irritates the lungs. You may be more likely to get serious lung infections, such as pneumonia. Other common recreational drugs, such as cocaine or crystal methamphetamine (also known as "meth" or "speed" or "crank" and "Tina"), can leave your body dehydrated and exhausted, as well as lead to skin irritation. All of these things can make it easier for you to get infections. The organ in your body that alcohol and other drugs affect most is your liver. The liver rounds up waste from chemicals that you put in your body. Those chemicals include recreational drugs as well as prescription drugs, such as your HIV medications. A weaker liver means less efficient "housekeeping" and, probably, a weaker you. If you also have hepatitis C (or any other kind of hepatitis), your liver is already working very hard to fight the disease itself and deal with the strong drugs that you may be taking for your hepatitis treatment.

DRUGS AND ALCOHOL: INTERACTIONS WITH YOUR HIV MEDS

HIV medications are hard on your body, so when you are taking these drugs, it is important that your liver works as well as possible. The liver is responsible for getting rid of waste products from the medications. Once you are HIV positive, your body may react differently to alcohol and drugs. Many people find that it takes longer to recover from using pot, alcohol, or other recreational drugs than it did before they had HIV. Remember that having HIV means a major change has taken place in your body. You may choose to use alcohol and drugs in moderation but be sure to respect your body. Pay attention to what and how much you eat, drink, smoke, and take into your body. Certain HIV medications can boost the level of recreational drugs in your system in unexpected and dangerous ways. For example, amphetamines (such as crystal meth) can be present at 3 to 22 times their normal levels in the bloodstream when mixed with an HIV drug called ritonavir (Norvir). That's because ritonavir hampers the body's ability to break down these other drugs. If you are going to mix a recreational drug with any medication, it is better to start with a very low amount of the recreational drug (as low as 1/4 the normal amount) and allow time to see how it affects you before increasing the amount. Keep in mind that, as recreational drugs aren't regulated, you never know exactly how much you are getting. Although you may feel uncomfortable at first, you should tell your doctor what recreational drugs you are using. That way, your doctor will know how the substances you are using affect your HIV drugs and your overall health. Most likely, telling your doctor will help explain some things going on in your body.

DRUGS, ALCOHOL, AND SAFER SEX

Certain drugs, such as methamphetamine, affect your ability to make decisions. Even though you use condoms regularly and practice safer sex when you're not high, you may be willing to take more risks and not use a condom when you're under the influence of methamphetamine or other drugs. Alcohol can also affect the decisions you make about safer sex. For example, if you have too much to drink, you may not be able to remember where you put the condoms and decide simply not to use them. These are decisions you probably would not make if you were sober. These actions put your partner at risk for HIV and put you at risk for other sexually transmitted diseases. Remember to keep condoms handy in places where you might have sex. Also, try to limit the amount of alcohol you drink if you know you are going to have sex.

HIV AND INJECTION DRUG USE

Sharing a needle when injecting drugs is dangerous for you and for the people you are sharing with. They could get HIV from you, and you could get another disease, such as hepatitis, from them. The safest option is not to share. Use clean needles each time or keep your own needles to yourself. Because of the dangers of injection drug use, the best way to lower your risk is to stop injecting drugs and to enter and complete a substance abuse treatment plan. You can talk to your health care provider about this. If you do inject drugs, follow these reminders:

- Never reuse or "share" syringes, water, or drug preparation equipment.
- Use only syringes obtained from a reliable source (such as drugstores or needle exchange programs).
- Use a new, sterile syringe each time to prepare and inject drugs.
- If possible, use sterile water to prepare drugs; otherwise, use clean water from a reliable source (such as fresh tap water).
- Use a new or disinfected container ("cooker") and a new filter ("cotton") to prepare drugs.
- Clean the injection site with a new alcohol swab prior to injection.
- Safely dispose of syringes after one use.

KICKING THE HABIT: HIV AND SMOKING

Smoking cigarettes is the leading cause of preventable death in the United States. And smoking is even worse for people with HIV than it is for people without HIV. Among persons living with HIV/AIDS, smoking is closely linked with heart disease and serious lung diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), emphysema, chronic bronchitis, and asthma. It also is associated with several of types of cancer. Take a look at the [HIV and Tobacco Use Fact Sheet](#) to learn more. Quitting smoking is a powerful way you can improve your health. There are many smoking cessation programs through the [American Cancer Society](#) and the American Heart Association for [nicotine](#) and [vaping](#).

DRUGS AND ALCOHOL: POINTS TO REMEMBER

- Most people are willing to take some risks, and using drugs and alcohol is no exception. But when alcohol or other drugs become an escape that you rely upon, it can be dangerous to your mental and physical health.
- Before you drink or use drugs, it is important to think about what risks you are willing to take.
- If you would like to cut back on your use of alcohol or other drugs, talk to your case manager or your doctor about getting help and finding the treatment you need.

Change Plan Contract

DATE: _____

PRIMARY SUBSTANCE: ALCOHOL CANNABIS DRUG _____
(Specify)

I AGREE TO THE FOLLOWING GOAL:

I WILL QUIT COMPLETELY.

I WILL CONTINUE TO USE LESS.

I WILL CUT DOWN

I WILL CONTINUE TO NOT DRINK OR USE DRUGS.

I WILL TAKE MY PRESCRIPTION MEDICATIONS ONLY AS PRESCRIBED.

TO ACHIEVE MY GOAL, MY NEXT STEP(S) IS/ARE:

WHEN: _____

I WILL: _____

WHEN: _____

I WILL: _____

SPECIFIC REFERRAL(S) WILL BE TO:

SIGNATURES

Client

Case Manager

SECTION IV APPENDICES

The graphics that follow may be used for your reference as you continue to learn MI and MIBI.

SPIRIT OF MI DIAGRAM

The 4 Tasks of **MOTIVATIONAL** INTERVIEWING

MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEW

Hill

The DARN CAT Tool

.....

STAGES OF CHANGE

PREPARATORY CHANGE TALK

- Desire
- Ability
- Reasons
- Need

MOBILIZING CHANGE TALK

- Commitment
- Activation
- Taking Steps

STAGES OF CHANGE

- Pre-Contemplation
- Contemplation
- Preparation
- Action

OVERVIEW OF MI

MIBI STEPS

1

Engage & Focus

Engage with OARS
and
Focus on Primary
Substance Use

2

Evoke

Evoke commitment
to change

1. Reasons to Cut Back/Quit
2. Provide Feedback
3. Importance or Confidence Strategy

3

Plan

Create a feasible
plan together

1. Goal
2. Steps (When)
3. Services
4. Supports
5. Obstacles

4

Summarize

Keep the Door
Open or Change
Plan Contract

Importance or Confidence Rulers

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The Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF) Strategy

ISF

IMPLEMENTATION &
SUSTAINMENT FACILITATION

Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy

INTRODUCTION

Research has clearly shown that evidence-based practice (EBP) adoption requires effective implementation, and that effective implementation requires support.

The Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy (ISF) provides the tools and strategies that enable an Implementation Advisor to support an organizational team in the successful implementation of an EBP.

This ISF Strategy manual and the website (ISFStrategy.org) have been developed to bridge the gap between research and practice by providing Implementation Advisors (IAs) with the tools and strategies needed to effectively coach organizations to EBP implementation success. This manual does not offer a comprehensive exploration of implementation facilitation.

HOW TO USE THIS MANUAL

The purpose of this manual is to provide the practical information a facilitator needs as a coach or supervisor to effectively work with a team and implement a new practice.

This ISF manual focuses on the core ISF Strategy elements (strategies and tools) listed below and found on the ISF website (ISFStrategy.org). Although these tools can be used in a number of ways, they are presented in this manual following a sequence that represents three phases of an implementation process.

Implementation Process for EBP

- Phase 1: Initial Engagement & Planning
- Phase 2: Preparation for Implementation
- Phase 3: Active Implementation & Sustainment Planning

As the details of specific implementations sequences will vary, these three phases are best understood as a reflection of a **continuum of implementation supports through a typical EBP implementation**. IAs should feel comfortable using the tools and strategies at any points in the implementation sequence. In addition to these core ISF elements, we have identified some additional tools and strategies in each phase that will be useful in implementations of EBPs. Prior to exploring these phases, we will briefly review the foundations of ISF.

- A. Core ISF Strategies and Tools
- B. The ISF Relational Framework for Process Implementation
- C. The Four Processes of Motivational Interviewing: Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan

A. Core ISF Strategies and Tools

The core ISF elements integrate effective strategies with interactive tools designed to engage staff in the implementation of EBPs within the organization (see Figure 1).

ISF Strategies:

- Using an Implementation Advisor (IA).
- Developing tools for Quality Improvement.
- Organizing Implementation team meetings.
- Identifying and preparing champions.

Figure 1. ISF Strategies

ISF TOOLS		
Workbook Tracking Tool		Creating structure for the team process, and gathering key information to support the EBP implementation.
Decision Balance (DB) Exercise		Weighing the Pros and Cons of EBP implementation.
Past Implementation Effort (PIE) Exercise		Exploring past implementations to understand strengths and risks associated with the current effort.
Performance Review and Planning (PREP) Exercise		Engaging in a data driven review of recent and current efforts to develop implementation plans.
Implementation and Climate Evaluation (ICE) Exercise		Understanding the organizational climate: Does it expect, support, and reward the EBP implementation?

For those who are interested in a broader document regarding the range of skills and tools related to facilitation, these manuals might be helpful:

- Getting to Outcomes: <https://www.rand.org/health-care/projects/getting-to-outcomes.html>
- Using Implementation Facilitation to improve care in the Veterans health Administration <https://www.queri.research.va.gov/tools/implementation.cfm>

B. The ISF Relational Framework for Process Implementation

Successful use of the ISF strategy must be built upon a framework of a strong relationship between the IA and the organizational team. The tools and strategies serve to further develop this relationship and support the implementation effort. The foundational framework elements described below ensure that the IA engages the organizational team with empathy and builds a trusting relationship that will yield results.

1. Role of an IA
2. Cultural competency
3. Facilitation of virtual implementation
4. Motivational interviewing to support EBP implementation

1. *ROLE OF AN IA*

“Advisor,” “Coach,” “Facilitator,” and “Consultant” are examples of multiple names that have been used to describe the role of the individual who provides technical assistance to an implementation effort. Although the IA may provide a substantial amount of content knowledge regarding the EBP, **the primary role of the IA is to support the implementation process.**

Many implementations tend to focus more of their resources on the “what” (the details of the EBP) and less of their resources on the “how” (the process of implementation).

How the IA assists with process implementation:

- The IA works with the team to rebalance this approach, ensuring that the process of implementation includes all steps necessary for success.
- The use of an IA is listed first among the ISF strategies for a reason. The IA role is the source of support for the utilization of the strategies and ISF tools.
- The IA serves as a facilitator to assist the team in implementing EBPs. We describe the IA as an “outside expert,” as the IA is not typically a member of the team or organization implementing an EBP but is a supportive resource brought to the team as a consultant or coach to guide the implementation process.
- The *external* support of an IA often provides dedicated resources and a neutral voice promoting implementation that has distinct advantages over the use of an internal staff member. Some implementation models encourage a partnership between an internal and an external facilitator.

Although tools and strategies are critical, **trust lies at the heart of any effective implementation effort.** As such, IA effectiveness is rooted in both expertise (specific knowledge, skills, and experiences) and interpersonal skills. IAs must communicate a clear understanding of the implementation challenges of a team. It is this empathy for the team’s process challenges that enables a trusting partnership.

2. *ORGANIZATION CULTURAL COMPETENCY*

The famous management consultant Peter Drucker is often quoted as having said that “Culture eats strategy for breakfast.” The culture of an organization and the contributing cultures of the individuals within that organization have a tremendous impact on everything that the organization does. Culture is a critical factor in developing a climate that is promotional of change implementation. Successful IA support leverages technical content guidance with implementation acumen well-suited to the site culture. To effectively support an organization in the implementation of an EBP, an IA must invest the time and energy needed to understand the cultures of the stakeholders. This will enable the IA to align the implementation with these cultural values and beliefs.

3. *FACILITATION OF VIRTUAL IMPLEMENTATION*

The ISF model was developed with the majority of the IA-team communication occurring through the use of video and telephonic conferencing. This model enables coaches to engage teams to work on EBP

implementation without concerns for geographic proximity. Each of the ISF tools can be performed via virtual conferencing.

The ISF model typically includes a site visit that brings the IA to the site of EBP implementation. This site visit enables the IA to enhance the relationship with the implementation team. Organization culture and mission are often best understood through a site visit. The impact of several of the tools described in Phase 1 of this manual can be amplified when they are conducted as part of a site visit, as the IA works to understand site-specific assets and challenges related to implementation.

COVID-19 has resulted in a need to adjust the ISF model to exclude site visits and to replace them with additional video conferencing activities. An expansion of video conference utilization will likely create a permanent shift toward reduced site visitation. A number of the tools that are typically conducted live can be done effectively via a video conference (e.g., staff using a cell phone or tablet camera to give the IA a tour of the service site and conduct an experiential walk-through of the service experience). Although these adaptations can be effective, IAs are encouraged to be mindful of the potential impact of live site visits and to consider their use when circumstances allow.

4. *MOTIVATIONAL INTERVIEWING TO SUPPORT EBP IMPLEMENTATION*

How often do people make decisions with 100% certainty? With rare exceptions, we all experience a level of ambivalence about any substantial decision that we need to make.

Motivational interviewing (MI) is rooted in the Stages of Change model (see Figure 2) and recognizes the importance of helping people explore their uncertainty in the early stages of change. Consider two people holding the ends of a rope. When one tries to pull the other in a direction before reaching agreement, the most likely reaction is a pull in the other direction. The “tug of war” that emerges is too often represented in efforts to promote change. Efforts to pull an individual, team, or system toward change almost always results in intensified ambivalence and strong resistance.

Systems seeking to implement EBPs experience the same range of ambivalence seen in any change effort. Despite volumes of research regarding the benefits of EBPs, individuals and organizations are concerned about the return on their investment of resources. An MI/Stages of Change approach to support EBP implementation will result in more effective engagement and a more rapid development and execution of an implementation plan.

Figure 2. Stages of Change Model

Motivational Interviewing (MI) is a counseling technique created by Miller and Rollnick designed to encourage behavior change by helping people to resolve this ambivalence.

C. The Four Processes of Motivational Interviewing: Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan

Throughout this ISF manual you will see multiple references to these core MI principles (see Addendum A) along with a summary of the key actions associated with each of the four MI processes:

1. ENGAGE
2. FOCUS
3. EVOKE
4. PLAN

Do’s & Don’ts for Effective Motivational Interviewing-Informed Interventions

MI Do’s: How To Explore Change Ideas	MI Don’ts: What To Avoid In Exploring Change Ideas
Affirm strengths	Unsolicited advice
Foster collaboration	Directions
Motivate for change	Feedback
Develop discrepancies in thinking	Promoting the new behavior
Explore pros and cons	Confrontation
Explore ambivalence	Assertions of authority
Provide client-centered feedback	Closed-ended (yes/no) questions

MI Process #1: Engage

The acronym “OARS” is used to remember the four key elements of the engagement process.

- **O**pened-ended questions
- **A**ffirmations
- **R**eflections
- **S**ummarizing

Open-ended questions (Why? How? Can you tell me more about that?) and encouragements to describe thoughts, feelings, and concerns aid the engagement process. Closed-ended questions (those with yes or no answers, or requests for specific information) tend to discourage engagement and appreciation of the sharer’s perspective. Appreciation for the experience and perspective of the party considering an EBP implementation and reflections that restate those perspectives help them know they are being understood with empathy. Summarizing statements from the IA that gather up the key elements of their story aid this perception of empathy and prepare them for the processes below.

MI Process #2: Focus

"Why are you here?" This question summarizes the essence of the focusing process of MI. Those who are considering an EBP implementation need guidance and direction from an IA. The IA should follow their lead and seek to understand the motivations for considering the EBP. The IA can assist by helping to map out options related to the implementation and by focusing on particular issues that need further attention.

MI Process #3: Evoke

The acronym “DARN CAT” is used to remember the elements of the evocation process in MI.

Preparatory change talk: DARN

- **D**esire to change
- **A**bility to change
- **R**eason to change
- **N**eed to change

Mobilizing change talk: CAT

- **C**ommitment to change
- **A**ctivation to change
- **T**aking steps to change

A team may tell the IA that they have a strong need to implement an EBP, based on their understanding of how the EBP can improve their services, but they may not have the ability to complete the implementation without some changes to their current priorities. Other teams may be ambivalent about the value of the EBP when compared with other current practices. The IA can explore these issues with the team to move toward an active commitment to take steps toward implementing the EBP.

Open-ended questions are again critical in this process phase, as the IA explores the potential implementers’ thoughts and feelings. “Are you willing and able to implement this EBP? What are your reasons for doing so? How committed are you and your team to taking action to get started?”, etc.

MI Process #4: Plan

Is the team ready to take active steps to plan the implementation of the EBP? Is there a clear path or sequence that needs to be followed? What supports can the IA offer to the team to aid in this implementation planning? Just as in the engagement process #1, the IA should use OARS in the planning process to support the team's efforts.

- Opened-ended questions
 - Affirmations
 - Reflections
 - Summarizing
-

Implementation Process for EBP

- Phase 1: Initial Engagement & Planning
- Phase 2: Preparation for Implementation
- Phase 3: Active Implementation & Sustainment Planning

PHASE 1: Initial Engagement & Planning

Use the ISF Tool: The ISF Implementation and Climate Evaluation (ICE) Exercise

[See Tool Here](#)

Too often organizations encourage staff to seek training in EBPs and then expect effective implementation without providing adequate resources. The result is often an implementation that lacks fidelity and sustainment.

An organizational climate that promotes a new EBP is critical to implementation success. The ICE Exercise helps teams to explore the degree to which their implementation climate expects, supports, and rewards the chosen EBP so that course corrections can be made to ensure greater implementation success.

Question Categories for ICE	
<i>Is the EBP expected?</i>	Are structures in place that measure the level and volume of utilization of the EBP among trained staff?
<i>Is the EBP supported?</i>	Do leaders provide resources and encouragement to maintain and increase EBP utilization?
<i>Is the EBP rewarded?</i>	Are those who implement the EBP provided with incentives to encourage their efforts?

5 TIPS WHEN USING ICE

1. Consider the three question categories as open-ended discussion prompts.
2. Encourage a full consideration of each of the three primary questions (Expected, Supported, Rewarded) by asking participants to share examples and descriptions of the corresponding operational questions (What are the structures, resources and incentives?)
3. Cultivate dialogue by generating lists of response items and asking follow-up prompts (Can you explain? Tell me more?, Tell me why?, etc.)

How does ICE promote the MI processes?

- Engage: Use ICE questions to engage.
- Focus: Use ICE to gain clarity regarding the organizational direction.
- Evoke: Use ICE to prepare and mobilize for the EBP implementation.
- Plan: Use ICE responses to structure implementation planning efforts.

Use the ISF Tool: ISF Decisional Balance (DB) Exercise

[See Tool Here](#)

Most of us have used a “Pros” and “Cons” list when making a decision. A thoughtful review of the reasons for and against an action is often a critical step toward decision making. When systems seek to implement EBPs, it can be easy to emphasize the value of the new practice without considering some of the challenges or difficulties that might result from the effort. The use of the Decisional Balance (DB) Exercise encourages team members to consider both the upside and the downside to an EBP implementation.

Rather than discouraging the team, this effort can surface some of the practical considerations that must be addressed to ensure an effective adoption of the EBP. These can include limited funds or staff resources, potential customer reactions to the new practice, or other stressors related to the change. This realistic assessment of the EBP is further encouraged through the four-quadrant approach to the Pros/Cons analysis.

Figure 3: Four-quadrant Approach to EBP Implementation Pros/Cons Analysis

These last two questions generate additional layers of analysis to encourage a fully informed analysis for the team (*How will we benefit if we don't implement this practice? Will we be missing out? etc.*). A thorough exploration of the DB is likely to create a stronger and more confident decision, which will aid the team's implementation effort.

5 TIPS FOR USING DB

1. Use a variety of synonyms to engage the thinking of participants.
2. Pros are the “upside,” advantage, positives, or reasons to do it.
3. Cons are the “downside,” disadvantage, negatives, or reasons to avoid it.
4. Restate questions three and four (pros and cons to not implementing the EBP) in different ways and allow people time to consider the difference between these later two questions and the first two questions (pros and cons to implementing the EBP).
5. Encourage a high volume of idea generation that includes all participants. This may include a need to seek feedback from less active team members.

How does the DB promote the four MI processes?

- Engage: Use the DB to engage staff in a conversation about the benefits of MI.
- Focus: Use the DB to explore options.
- Evoke: Use the DB to address ambivalence and create clarity regarding EBP implementation.
- Plan: Use the DB to create lists of details that will aid in the planning process.

Use the ISF Strategy: Assessing for readiness and identifying barriers

Given our current state, how likely are we to succeed with the implementation and sustainment of the chosen EBP? There are a number of ways to consider the readiness of a team and organization to implement an EBP. Although general meetings and structured dialogues among stakeholders can help assess readiness, the tools below can all be used to identify assets that will support implementation and alleviate barriers that will hinder implementation.

How does the use of readiness assessment tools promote the four MI processes?

- Engage: Use assessment tools to understand the organizational climate for EBP implementation.
- Focus: Use assessment tools to understand the organizational goals and direction.
- Evoke: Use assessment tools to surface the organizational need for change.
- Plan: Use assessment tools to create context for EBP planning.

Additional Tools:

- SWOT/SOAR
- Environmental scan
- Empathy map
- Cause and effect diagram

SWOT/SOAR

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis is a commonly used planning tool to explore elements that are internal to an organization (SW) and those that are external to the organization in the larger environment (OT). See Addendum B.

Some find the SWOT analysis, with a focus that includes weaknesses and threats, to be a challenge for teams that lack confidence and motivation. A strength-based alternative to the SWOT analysis is the Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results (SOAR) tool, which focuses on the following four questions. For additional details and related questions, see Addendum C.

Figure 4: Strength-based SWOT Analysis Tool: SOAR

In addition to the formal SWOT and SOAR tools, it may also be helpful to ask key questions that explore the organizational culture and mission:

- Where have we been?
- Where are we going?
- What do we do?
- How do we do it?
- Why do we do it? (What is our contribution?)

5 TIPS FOR USING SWOT AND SOAR

1. Underscore the distinction in the SWOT between Strengths and Weaknesses, which are internal, and Opportunities and Threats, which are external, to ensure that content is generated in all four quadrants and ends up in the correct quadrant.
2. Encourage a long list in each quadrant.
3. When teams are feeling anxious or lack confidence, consider starting with the SOAR to build motivation and energy.
4. Explore variations on these question themes to generate a full understanding of the team's experience.
5. Include diverse stakeholders.

ENVIRONMENTAL SCAN

The environmental scan tool (see Addendum D) considers social, economic, and technological trends in both the macro (nation or state) and micro (local) environments. A thoughtful review of these factors can help assess the level of resources and supports available for an implementation effort. Is a planned implementation aligned with a strong current in the broader environment that will carry it down stream rapidly, or is the implementation swimming “upstream,” and meeting resistance at every turn? Such knowledge is critical to understanding the likelihood of success.

Tips for using Environmental Scan:

- « Encourage participants to generate ideas in each category.
- « Involve diverse stakeholders to ensure that voices with experience in all of the categories are included.

EMPATHY MAP

The empathy map (see Addendum E) is a simple and effective tool for cultivating an understanding of a stakeholder's experience. Engagement of stakeholders is improved dramatically when we explore what they say and do, and then consider how that reflects what they think and feel, and what their goals may be. The resulting insights into the motivations of stakeholders can support more effective strategic communications and partnership building.

Tips for using Empathy Map:

- « Work from left to right: start with what people say and do, and then consider what they think and feel.
- « Try to capture immediate goals and long-term goals.
- « Generate multiple ideas in each box.
- « Consider how you might have a better understanding of the subject after completing the Empathy Map.

CAUSE AND EFFECT DIAGRAM

Addendum F describes the cause and effect diagram, or Ishikawa diagram. A better understanding of the root causes of a problem can be helpful when considering the potential impact of a new EBP implementation. If our high-profile problem X is actually caused by Y, which is in turn caused by Z, we need to consider whether or not a proposed EBP will effectively address root cause Z.

Tips for using the Cause and Effect diagram:

- « Use the circular version of the tool, rather than the fishbone model, as it will be easier to manage the visual presentation of the data.
 - « Try to generate a large volume of causes at each level of the process. Try to find at least four causes for the initial problem, four sub-causes for each cause, four sub-sub-causes for each sub-cause, etc.
 - « Try to generate at least four levels of causes.
 - « Use the cause and effect diagram with other tools (e.g., complete a nominal group technique to brainstorm how to address a chosen sub-cause that seems to have a big impact).
-

PHASE 2: Preparation for Implementation

Securing the common and authoritative endorsements of an EBP by stakeholders enables an organization or a system to focus on strategic steps to properly fit the EBP to the local context. Strategically preparing for implementation reduces resistance, errors, and costs associated with implementation and strengthens roots essential for sustainability.

ISF TOOL: The ISF Past Implementation Effort (PIE) Exercise

[See Tool Here](#)

Often, the best predictor of a future implementation is a past implementation. Despite significant changes in staffing and other variables, organizational cultures tend to remain stable across time. The Past Implementation Effort (PIE) Exercise is designed to help organizations consider a previous implementation effort in order to gain insights related to the current effort. Significant insights can be gained from both successful and unsuccessful past implementations, but the PIE Exercise seems to be most effective when considering a past implementation that was at least partially successful. In addition to raising key strengths to be harnessed, or concerns to be addressed, the PIE conversation also helps build self-awareness regarding organizational process patterns. *We tend to do X in situation Y.*

Tips for using PIE:

- « Ask prompting questions to encourage the team to tell the story and provide details regarding the previous implementation.
- « Take notes that the team can see that underscore the primary process elements of the story to orient the team to the importance of process and the patterns of their organizational processes.
- « Generate a volume of ideas regarding the past implementation that reflect both the strength of the implementation and the challenges or lessons learned.
- « Find a way to summarize the content generated as a lens into understanding the resources that the team will bring to bear upon the new implementation effort. (What are the things that we need to do again with this new effort?)
- « Find a way to also underscore how the lessons learned can be helpful guidance to ensuring success. (What are the struggles that we want to avoid repeating?)

Consider asking team members to bring an actual pie to the meeting. 😊

How does the ISF PIE promote the four MI processes?

- Engage: Use PIE to affirm previous implementation efforts and lessons learned.
- Focus: Use PIE to discuss how lessons learned inform efforts related to MI implementation.
- Evoke: Use PIE to better understand an organizations ability to implement change.
- Plan: Use PIE to better understand strengths and weakness that will impact the planning process.

Core ISF Strategy: Conducting local consensus discussions

A range of tools and strategies can be used to create consensus among implementation team members and stakeholders. Facilitating a process with open-ended questions can lead to thoughtful dialogue. Brainstorming processes are also useful in planning specific actions. The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) is a structured brainstorming process that can assist the team in generating ideas for strategies to address the concern. See Addendum G.

The NGT is particularly helpful following the completion of a flow chart (see below) as teams seek to develop a focus on a particular concern and consider possible solutions to address the concern.

How do local consensus discussions promote the four MI processes?

- Engage: Use Consensus discussions to ask questions and seek understanding of the team.
- Focus: Use Consensus discussions to clarify a sense of direction.
- Evoke: Use Consensus discussions to develop alignment within the system regarding the readiness for change
- Plan: Use Consensus discussions to make decisions and take action.

Tips for using NGT:

- « Encourage adherence to the sequence of steps and the process outlined for each, by reminding participants that the rules for NGT have been well researched and carefully developed. (Maintain silence during idea generation; gather ideas using a round robin style instead of each person sharing multiple ideas at a time; etc.)
- « Encourage a large volume of ideas. When people seem to be done, encourage them to consider new possibilities.
- Try to use the original language presented by each participant. Avoid edits and paraphrases.
- Encourage people to try to keep their ideas short, like bumper stickers.
- Avoid all premature discussion and judgment of ideas.
- If ideas are sorted and similar ideas are merged, be careful not to lose any unique ideas in the mergers.
- When voting for ideas, consider using the following criteria. Good ideas are those that will achieve the desired result and require a manageable level of resource.
- Remind the group that all ideas will be retained as a resource for further consideration, after an idea has been chosen for action.

Core ISF Strategy: Identifying and preparing champions

The three roles described below (Local Champion, Executive Sponsor [ES], and Change Team) are the critical resources required for the successful implementation of an EBP. Although an IA may work primarily with the Local Champion, a connection to the ES and the Change Team are important to a full understanding of the systemic dynamics of EBP implementation.

How does the identification and preparation of champions promote the four MI processes?

- Engage: Use relationships with the champions to connect to the key stakeholders in the organization.
- Focus: Use relationships with the champions to understand the various perspectives regarding EBP implementation within the organizational system.
- Evoke: Use relationships with the champions to prepare and mobilize for change.
- Plan: Use relationships with the champions to plan steps toward EBP implementation.

The Local Champion, or change leader (CL), is the leader of the implementation team and is the critical on-site partner to the IA for the EBP implementation. The CL facilitates the Change Team and communicates the progress of the project to the ES (see below). If the IA is the architect working to design and plan the implementation effort with the organization, the CL serves as the builder or general contractor. The CL provides the “boots on the ground” management of the implementation details.

Implementation efforts require a team approach. Two additional roles below are important to EBP implementation and are also used in the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) improvement model discussed below in Phase 3. An effective IA works with the team in a manner that is both “bottom up” by empowering team members to generate ideas and make decisions and “top down” by cultivating the leadership role in supporting the implementation.

Tips for choosing a CL:

- « CLs should be:
 - an energetic supporter of the effort,
 - able to facilitate meetings effectively,
 - well connected to the ES, and
 - trusted and respected by the team members.

The ES provides senior leadership for any implementation or change effort. Although typically not involved in the day-to-day functions of the implementation effort, the ES ensures that adequate resources are available and empowers the CL and team by “green lighting” the project. The ES may also provide critical support in assessing the economic viability or “business case” for the implementation. This is a critical function, given that few implementations survive if they drain resources from the organization.

Tips for choosing an ES:

- « An ES should
 - provide resources and support,
 - communicate the value of the project to the entire staff, and
 - respond to the needs of the team in a timely manner.

The Implementation Team includes the staff members who are critical to the EBP roll out. It is best to include five to seven members with a range of experiences and roles. This group is convened regularly and managed by the Change Leader, and is supported by the IA in their sequence of implementation activities.

Tips for building a Change Team:

- « Seek motivated volunteers.
- « Include diverse roles and perspectives.
- « Include people with content knowledge and experience relevant to the implementation effort.
- « Include influencers who can market the project to the broader system.

Additional Tool: Flow chart

A flow chart or process map is an excellent tool for visually representing a process and discovering challenges or problems in the sequence of steps. It can be particularly helpful to role play the process of the EBP implementation in a “walk-through” exercise, and then draw a flow chart map of the sequence. This effort can reveal flaws in the process and lead the team to consider potential strategies for improvements to ensure that the EBP is delivered effectively. See Addendum H for more details about the flow chart process.

Tips for using a Flow Chart:

- « Use simple symbols (boxes and arrows, and diamonds for yes/no decision points).
 - « Avoid trying to flow chart your entire process. Select a specific portion of the process and document it in detail. Start by including a box that starts the process and a box that ends the process, and then fill in the middle steps.
-

- « Try to find the most useful level of detail. Flow charts that are too simple do not explain the process. Flow charts with too much detail that are confusing, hard to read, and paralyzing to the team.
- « Remember that challenges can occur in both the process steps (boxes) as well as in the transitions between steps (arrows).
- « Do not try to draw a flow chart of your desired process. Complete a flow chart of your current state, as this will reveal the flaws and challenges that need to be addressed.

Additional Strategy: Workforce training

Most EBP implementations require staff training to ensure that the team is able to manage and deliver the new practice. Although the focus of this manual is on process facilitation, providing adequate training to the team and staff so that they are confident and knowledgeable as they commence the provision of the new EBP is also important.

PHASE 3: Active Implementation and Sustainment Planning

Translating implementation plans and preparations into action requires active effort and oversight. This iterative and continual process lines up data and observations into a structure that enables decision making and adjustments to achieve the organizational team goals.

Core ISF Tool: The ISF Workbook Tracking Tool

[See Tool Here](#)

Teams benefit from a clear and consistent tracking of activities and progress across time. The Workbook Tracking Tool tracks elements of the implementation process across time, including team attendance, meeting notes, and members perceptions of performance. Returning to this familiar tracking tool with each meeting creates a stabilizing consistency and structure to team meetings, and helps team members see their progress and communicate action steps.

Tips for using the Workbook Tracking Tool:

- « Share the workbook in each meeting with the team and engage in concurrent documentation of the process.
- « Allow the team members some time to develop a consensus regarding how they will rate their performance, rather than seeking a rating from the leader, or most vocal member of the team. (Cultivate multiple opinions to add to the dialogue of the team.)
- « Share the completed workgroup with team members after each session to reinforce the discussion, lessons learned, and next planned activities.

How does the ISF Workbook promote the four MI processes?

Use the Workbook Tracking Tool to document all of the contacts with the team related to the EBP implementation and to share the workbook document with them after each encounter. This will reinforce the ideas explored and lessons learned related to each of the four processes (Engage, Focus, Evoke, Plan).

Core ISF Tool: The ISF Performance Review and Planning (PREP) Exercise

[See Tool Here](#)

Consider a track coach who watches a sprinter run a race and then seeks to improve the runner's performance. Now consider a second coach who records multiple races run by that same sprinter, with data for speeds in each section of the course and video to analyze the sprinter's form. It seems clear that coach number two is likely to be far more effective in supporting improved performance.

Collecting and reviewing performance data is among the best ways to enhance performance. An empathic IA who encourages an honest dialogue about recent performance can help a team to target specific changes and set clear goals for improvement. Teams are often motivated by this data driven approach as their efforts are more likely to be rewarded by improvements in performance. The PREP exercise has wide applicability and underscores the importance of rooting all implementation efforts in clearly measured performance goals.

Tips for using PREP:

- « Engage the team with an interactive review of the data sheets that are being explored.
- « Provide energy and enthusiasm when review data, as some team members may be less motivated to have data discussions.
- « Link the data results to the mission of the project and the mission of the team members to maintain motivation.
- « Use questions to elicit opinions about the data from the team to cultivate learning and investment.
- « Maintain a strength-based approach that encourages progress and avoids judgment when teams do not reach targeted goals.

How does ISF PREP promote the four MI processes?

- Focus: Use PREP to enable the organization to share their current experience, direction, and motivations that are driven by data.
- Evoke: Use PREP to clarify the reasons and needs for change that may service to mobilize the organization toward the EBP implementation.
- Plan: Use PREP to support a data driven orientation to commencing the implementation planning process.

Core ISF Strategy: Organizing Implementation team meetings

Implementation teams should meet regularly under the guidance of the change leader, with the support of the IA. The frequency of team meetings is best dictated by the availability of performance data related to the implementation efforts. It can be helpful to think of the data as the fuel in the implementation team engine.

Change leaders should be supported by the IA in developing team structures that encourage inclusion and active participation. Simple documentation of meetings should be used to track efforts and share progress with key stakeholders. There is a wide array of resources available related to developing and maintaining work groups and committees, and IAs are encouraged to review that literature.

How do team meetings promote the four MI processes?

Use team meetings to ensure that all parts of the process are inclusive of the key stakeholders. Although some individual meetings with ES and Local Champions are helpful to enable privacy to explore implementation challenge, the IA should maintain a strong connection to the team to promote progress in all processes (Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan).

Core ISF Strategy: Conducting cyclical small tests of change

Once an initial implementation has been established the IA can work with the team to find ways to improve the utilization of the EBP. Some of the tools described above (i.e., walk-through, flow chart, NGT, cause and effect diagram) are all helpful for gathering ideas for potential improvements. The rapid cycle PDSA improvement model (see Addendum I) is a widely utilized strategy for testing improvement ideas. The PDSA model focuses on data driven changes based on simple and measurable changes. As this manual does not provide a comprehensive description of Rapid Cycle PDSA change, the resources below can assist with a further exploration of this topic.

- www.NIATx.net
 - www.IHI.org
-

How do cyclical tests of change promote the four MI processes?

Rapid cycle process improvement during the implementation of EBP supports the MI planning phase. IAs can support the team and CL in the exploration of ideas that can lead toward a PDSA cycle using a number of tools in this manual.

Sustainment

Far too often, EBPs that have been effectively implemented and have yielded excellent results are not sustained. This pattern represents a tremendous lost opportunity and a loss of all of the resources invested in the initial implementation. An effective IA can use the tools and strategies described above to build a strong infrastructure that can sustain the new practice. Such an infrastructure is critical as new priorities, staff turnover, or economic challenges threaten the new EBP.

The IA should work with the team to ensure that the organization dedicates the needed resources to ensure sustainability. Ongoing monitoring of key factors and key metrics aid the team in early identification of any drift away from the EBP practice standard and the engagement of rapid action to reset the practice approach. IAs can help teams develop a plan to monitor the key metrics with a specific action trigger in mind. (*If metric X dips below Y, then we need to engage in action step Z.*) Often the best action step is the reconvening of the team to address the concerns. The four questions below are a useful guide to assist the IA in supporting the team's effort to develop a sustainability plan. They center upon an effort to predict potential obstacles to sustainability and the critical importance of ongoing measurement.

1. What are the internal organizational factors that will increase or decrease our capacity to sustain this EBP?
2. What are the external environmental factors that increase or decrease our capacity to sustain this EBP?
3. What are the factors specific to this EBP that will increase or decrease our capacity to sustain it?
4. What are the manageable metrics that will enable us to track our sustainment of this EBP?

Tools utilized by the IA in both the Initial Engagement and Planning and the Preparation for Implementation phase are valuable to solicit input from the team about the actual implementation of EBP components and perceptions about why a component of the EBP or EBP itself should be sustained.

Core ISF Tool: The ISF Past Implementation Effort (PIE) Exercise

During the sustainment phase, the focus of the PIE exercise shifts away from a prior implementation effort and focuses on the actual implementation of the EBP or its components in the organization. Similar to how the PIE Exercise was conducted in the Preparation for Implementation phase, the exercise, as led by the IA, should focus on soliciting significant insights from the team about why EBP implementation was or was not successful.

Core ISF Tool: The ISF Decision Balance (DB) Exercise

During the sustainment phase, the IA and the Change Team can reframe the DB through the four-quadrant approach to the Pros/Cons analysis to conduct a realistic assessment of the importance within the organization to sustaining the EBP or specific components of the EBP.

1. What are the pros to sustaining the EBP?
 2. What are the cons to sustaining the EBP?
 3. What are the pros to not sustaining the EBP?
-

4. What are the cons to not sustaining the EBP?

The combined results from the PIE and DB Exercises will help the team identify potential challenges in sustaining the EBP in the organization. The team, with guidance from the IA, can then identify additional change efforts to strengthen the EBP implementation and can integrate these ideas into the sustain plan.

Core Sustainability Strategy: Developing a System for Ongoing Monitoring

A critical component of a sustainability plan is to develop a system for ongoing monitoring of outcomes in the organization. The ongoing monitoring system acts as a sustainability roadmap that allows staff and leadership in the organization to evaluate if the improvements are being maintained. Therefore, it is important to create a process for collecting and monitoring data that addresses the following questions:

- What outcomes will you track?
- Who will collect, track and share the data?
- How will the data be collected?
- How often will you review the data?
- Who will be involved in the review?

In the data monitoring process, the organization should review, and revisit goals associated with sustainment on a regular basis. Questions to consider during the process include: What is the data telling you? Are there any outliers that could be impacting the data?

The sustainability planning process should also utilize tools such as the NGT to identify potential red flags or triggers that might threaten successful sustainment (e.g., staff turnover) of the intervention. After identifying these potential issues, the organization should establish checklists to address red flags/triggers as or when they arise. For example, embed intervention training in new staff orientation or incorporate new processes of care into policies and procedures within the organization.

A successfully sustained change will become the new normal. It will become the expected practice in the organization. Eventually this sustained change will serve as a benchmark for future implementation, as part of the ongoing journey of continuous quality improvement.

Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy

Addendums

A: Motivational Interviewing Processes	2
B: SWOT Analysis	3
C: SOAR Tool	4
D: Environmental Scan Tool	5
E: Empathy Maps	6
F: Cause and Effect Diagram	7
G: Nominal Group Technique	8
H: Flow Charts	1
I: Rapid Cycle PDSA Testing	2

ADDENDUM A: Motivational Interviewing Processes

Do's: Affirm strengths—Foster collaboration—Motivation to change—Developing discrepancies—Explore pros & cons—

Explore ambivalence—Organization centered problem discussion and feedback.

Don'ts: Unsolicited advice—Directions—Feedback—Emphasizing abstinence/the new desired behavior—Direct confrontation—

Focus on Powerlessness/loss of control—Asserting authority—Closed ended questions

STAGES of CHANGE: Precontemplation, Contemplation, Preparation, Action, Maintenance

ADDENDUM B: SWOT Analysis

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) is a widely used planning tool to help you understand the strategic position of your organization or program. As you fill in the four boxes, be sure to differentiate between those items that are internal to your organization (SW) and those that are from the external environment (OT). This tool is best used as part of a team planning effort.

	Positive	Negative
Internal	Strengths: What do we do well? 	Weaknesses: What do we need to do better?
External	Opportunities: (community needs, market niches, etc.) 	Threats: (competition, fiscal/political climates, etc.)

ADDENDUM C: SOAR Tool

Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results (SOAR) is a strength-based alternative to the SWOT analysis. This tool is best used as part of a team planning effort.

<p><u>Strengths:</u> What makes us proud?</p>	<p><u>Opportunities:</u> How do we make sense of the opportunities in our environment?</p>
<p><u>Aspirations:</u> What do we care deeply about?</p>	<p><u>Results:</u> How do we know we are succeeding?</p>

ADDENDUM D: Environmental Scan Tool

Use the **Environmental Scan** to gain a deeper and broader understanding of your environment. Fill in the grid by considering both macro and micro system trends in each of the four categories. This tool is best used as part of a team planning effort. It will help you to chart a course that harnesses your resources and steers around avoidable obstacles.

	Macro Trends (State/National--broader culture)	Micro Trends (Local--your industry)
Social Demographic Trends		
Economic Trends		
Political/ Regulatory Trends		
Technolo gical Trends		

ADDENDUM E: Empathy Maps

Use empathy maps to better understand the perspective of an individual or a group.

The steps of Empathy Mapping:

- Place the name or key descriptors of the person or group you want to understand in the center circle.
- Ask each question below and give your team a few minutes to record their responses individually.
- Gather the content from the group.
- Start by exploring what the party says and does, as this can help in exploring what the party thinks and feels.

What do they **Say**?

What do they **Think**?

What do they **Feel**?

What do they **Do**?

What are their **Goals**? (add goal information below the four boxes.)

ADDENDUM F: Cause and Effect Diagram

The Cause and Effect diagram, also known as the fishbone or the Ishikawa diagram, is used to explore the root cause of a problem. Traditionally done in the shape of a fish, the facilitator asks a group to consider a problem, and then asks for the causes of the problem and the causes of the causes, until all potential root causes have been explored.

Others prefer a **hub and spoke approach**, as it is easier to draw and expand with a group:

- Define the problem in a center circle and draw a cause circle at each of the four compass headings.
- Ask the group to define at least these four causes (there may be more) and place them in the circles.
- Then explore the sub causes of these four causes and continue until all causes have been explored. The result will be an inventory of granular root causes, some of which will be excellent targets for improvement.

ADDENDUM G: Nominal Group Technique

The Nominal Group Technique is a brainstorming technique that will ensure team member inclusion and the generation of a high volume of diverse ideas.

The four steps of NGT

1. **Silent Generation of ideas based on a strong question:** Each individual generates their own list.
 2. **Round Robin Report and Record:** Go around the room, one idea per person, record and number ideas as stated for all to see.
 3. **Discussion for Clarification:** Questions are asked regarding the ideas shared. Ensure that all members understand all ideas.
 4. **Voting:** Using sticky dots, a show of hands, or anonymous paper votes. Allow individuals should be given a number of votes that encourages them to prioritize the best ideas. Criteria for voting may include the ideas impact and feasibility.
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ADDENDUM H: Flow Charts

Flow charts present a visual map of the process to show steps and transitions. They are helpful for finding bottle necks, road blocks, and other challenges that prevent a smooth flow in the service process.

These challenges are excellent targets for improvement.

Step 1: Draw the first and last step of the process you would like to flow chart.

Step 2: Fill in all the steps of the process (this can include decision steps by using diamonds).

Step 3: Note any flaws to the process: This step has elements that people complain about, this transition takes too long and leaves people waiting, etc. (Remember that flaws can be located in the steps and/or in the transitions.)

Step 4: Note any fixes for the flaws you have defined.

Step 5: Use the flow chart along with other tools to consider next steps for improvement projects.

 ADDENDUM I: Rapid Cycle PDSA Testing

Steps in the PDSA Change Process	Key Questions
Choose a goal.	<i>What do we want to improve?</i>
Choose a change.	<i>What changes will lead to the desired improvement?</i>
Plan to measure progress.	<i>How will we know if the change is working?</i>
PLAN the change.	<i>What are the resources and activities needed?</i>
DO the change.	<i>How do we implement our plan?</i>
STUDY the results.	<i>Can we adjust the change to make further progress toward our goal?</i>
ACT on the data and lessons learned.	<i>What have we learned?</i>
Multiple PDSA cycles (Adapt the change as needed, based upon our data results.)	<i>What are our next steps? (Adopt, abandon, or adapt the change?)</i>
Sustain the change.	<i>How can we maintain progress?</i>
Spread the change.	<i>How can we spread a successful change to a new team/location?</i>
